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CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D9: Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design v1.0

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Executive Summary

D9 (*CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design intermediate version*) is an intermediate deliverable of WP2 which covers the work developed in Tasks 2.2, 2.3, 2.4. This work corresponds to the first 6 months of the project development and relates with the following aspects: i) development of the initial design (high-level) of the CODECO framework architecture; ii) technological guidelines based on an extensive analysis of related work concerning the CODECO key innovation results; iii) guidelines and proposed best practices concerning experimentation and validation in CODECO; iv) open-source ecosystem development guidelines. D9 is provided as input to the technical work packages of CODECO, to drive the detailed specification of the project's components as well as their integration and validation in the project's use-cases across four different application domains.

Keywords: Edge-Cloud continuum; orchestration; Kubernetes; AI/ML; network; data; compute; context-awareness.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction	12
1.1 Document Scope	12
1.2 Dependencies	12
1.3 Document Structure	12
1.4 The CODECO Ecosystem	13
2 CODECO High-Level Architecture	14
2.1 Architectural Design Methodology	14
2.2 Terminology, K8s, and the Edge-Cloud Continuum	15
2.3 Framework Architecture	17
2.3.1 CODECO Workflow Example, One Cluster	21
2.3.2 CODECO Workflow Example, Federated Clusters	22
2.4 High-level Specification of CODECO Components	23
2.4.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management	23
2.4.2 MDM: Metadata Manager	28
2.4.3 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration	36
2.4.4 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness ..	42
2.4.5 NetMa: Network Management and Adaptation	51
3 CODECO Technological Guidelines	58
3.1 CODECO Contributions	58
3.1.1 Automated Configuration	58
3.1.2 Dynamic Scheduling and Workload Migration	60
3.1.3 Context-awareness and Privacy-Preserving Decentralised Learning	61
3.1.4 Cross-layer Network Adaptation	64
3.1.5 Data as a Resource	66
3.2 Potential synergies with HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01 call projects	67
3.3 Summary, CODECO Technological Guidelines	67
4 Global Validation Aspects	68
4.1 Experimentation Tools and Guidelines	68
4.1.1 Simulators, Emulators, Testbeds	68
4.1.2 Guidelines	69
4.2 CODECO Experimentation Environments	71
4.2.1 Use-case testbeds	71
4.2.2 CODECO Deployment and Implementation Environment	72
4.3 EdgeNet Experimentation Guidelines	74
5 Open-source CODECO Ecosystem Guidelines	75
5.1 Open-Source Governance and the Eclipse Development Process	76
5.2 Implementing Open-Source Best Practices: the Eclipse CODECO Research Lab	77
6 Summary and Next Steps	80
7 References	81
Annex I – Example of CODECO Metrics: Data, Compute, User, Network	87
Annex II – CODECO High-Level Architecture Interfaces	92

List of Figures

Figure 1: The CODECO ecosystem and target stakeholder groups.	13
Figure 2: High-level architectural design methodology.	15
Figure 3: K8s high-level operation, 1 cluster, roles in the master and worker nodes.	16
Figure 4: The CODECO K8s framework and its components.	19
Figure 5: CODECO high-level architecture.	20
Figure 6: ACM interaction points to CODECO components and external systems and users.	24
Figure 7: ACM and its sub-components, high-level specification.	26
Figure 8: CODECO monitoring architecture.	27
Figure 9: MDM high-level specification.	29
Figure 10: MDM API and its endpoints.	30
Figure 11: MDM single cluster operation.	34
Figure 12: MDM, initial operation aspects in federated clusters.	35
Figure 13: SWM high-level representation.	37
Figure 14: Current SWM CRs and objects.	39
Figure 15: PDLC high-level architecture and interfaces.	43
Figure 16: Examples of context-aware parameters in CODECO.	45
Figure 17: A sample data pre-processing pipeline used as a baseline for PDLC-DP.	47
Figure 18: Deployment and operation of PDLC within a single CODECO cluster.	51
Figure 19: NetMA high-level goals and interaction with CODECO components.	52
Figure 20: NetMA High-level architecture.	53
Figure 21: ALTO as network exposure function of the network.	56
Figure 22: High-level example of NetMA operation for federated clusters.	58
Figure 23: EdgeNet CRDs and features.	75
Figure 24: The Eclipse project creation process.	76
Figure 25: Eclipse Research Labs Phases.	78
Figure 26: CODECO open-source timeline.	79
Figure 27: The CODECO Eclipse GitLab repositories.	79

List of Tables

Table 1: ACM interfaces to other CODECO components.	27
Table 2: MDM interfaces to other CODECO components.	33
Table 3: SWM interfaces to other CODECO components.	41
Table 4: PDLC interfaces to other CODECO components.	50
Table 5: NetMA interfaces to other CODECO components.	56
Table 6: CODECO individual clusters and potential interconnections via a shared Cloud space.	73
Table 7: Minimum system requirements of technologies utilized by CODECO.	74

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, Accounting
ACM	Automated Configuration Manager
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
CA	Context-awareness
CD	Compute Domain
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CLI	Command Line Interface
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CNI	Container Network Interface
CP	Customer Premises
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CR	Custom Resource
DEV	Developer
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EDA	Encoder Decoder Architectures
EN	Edge Node
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standards Institute
FaaS	Function as a Service
FIDO	Fast Identity Online
FL	Federated Learning
GENEVE	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GNNs	Graph Neural Networks
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRU	Gate Recurrent
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Horizon Europe
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDS	International Data Spaces
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IP	Internet Protocol
IPSec	Internet Protocol Security
IPv6	Internet Protocol Version 6
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
K8s	Kubernetes
KCP	Kubernetes like Control Plane
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L2	Layer 2
L3	Layer 3
LSTM	Long-Short Term Memory
LTE	Long-term Evolution
MARL	Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning
MDM	Metadata Manager
MEC	Multi-access Edge computing
MGR	Infrastructure Manager
ML	Machine Learning
ND	Network Domain

Acronym	Meaning
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
NGIoT	Next Generation Internet of Things
NN	Neural Network
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OS	Operating System
OSS	Open-source system
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RL	Reinforced Learning
RFC	Request for Comments
SDN	Software Defined Network
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UI	User Interface
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VoIP	Voice over IP
VR	Virtual Reality
VXLAN	Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

List of Definitions

Term	Definition
Application	Computer software design to perform a single or several specific tasks, e.g., a calendar. In CODECO, an application is composed by at least one micro-service, i.e., applications are a collection of services that are loosely coupled, highly available, and independently deployable.
Application Programming Interface (API)	Well defined specification used in a software program to access services or resources provided by another software application. Establishes the interface between two different applications.
Cloud	IT environment that abstracts, pools, and shares IT resources across a network. A Cloud is a software-defined environment associated with hyperscale data centres, often far from the data sources or end-user.
Cloud computing	The act of running application workloads on a Cloud.
Cluster	A K8s cluster consists of the components that are a part of the control plane (master nodes) and worker nodes, where containerized applications run. A cluster corresponds to the logical environment where Pods run in a way that has been orchestrated by a human operator.
Consumer	See service recipient
Container	Container follows the K8s definition, where it is a package with the overall settings (workload, state, data) to allow execution of an application in an independent way. A container runs logically in a Pod.
Container manager	See orchestrator.
Container orchestrator	A tool that assists the setup and lifetime management of containerized applications. Examples of container orchestrators are K8s and Docker swarm.
CR	From K8s. CRs correspond to new objects (or instances of) defined by CRDs.

Term	Definition
	A custom resource is the API extension mechanism in Kubernetes.
CRD	From K8s. A custom resource definition (CRD) defines a CR and lists out all the configuration available to users of a K8s operator. Written in YAML it has a limit of 1 MiB due to being stored in the K8s etcd, which has been designed to handle small key value pairs typical for metadata. CRDs supply definitions for CRs, thus assisting in creating new types of resources without having to add another API server in K8s.
Edge	An IT environment that abstracts, pools, and supplies IT resource sharing in a location close to data sources (e.g., IoT devices, end-user). Place computing resources closer to the user or the device, at the “edge” of the network, rather than in a hyperscale cloud data centre that might be many miles away in the “core” of the network. CODECO adopts the terms supported far Edge and near Edge as in NGIOT [1].
Edge-Cloud continuum	The overall IT environment interconnecting and end-user to services running across the far Edge until the Cloud.
End-user	See user.
far Edge	The notion of far Edge reflects the elements located on customer premises, covering not only the existing cyber-physical systems but also the interfaces to the real-world, as well as context-awareness (e.g., situational awareness) required to perform local/partial decisions (storage, processing, analysis decisions) upon data collected 81. Hence, the far Edge embodies a full intertwining to the real-world which can only be provided via some form of context-awareness, behaviour inference and learning, i.e., integration of intelligence. Physically, the near Edge integrates the last mile concept. Applications that run on the far Edge are often time-sensitive, require ultra-low latency, high scalability, and high throughput. Examples are AR/VR, Gaming. Other used terms for far Edge are deep Edge, micro-Edge.
Interconnection	The physical and logical linking of public communications networks used by the same or a different undertaking to allow the users of one undertaking to communicate with users of the same or another undertaking, or to access services provided by another undertaking.
K8s control plane	The control plane is the system that can assist in defining, deploying, and managing the lifecycle of containers in a cluster. It continuously manages object states, responding to changes in the cluster and triggering changes to match a desired performance state. The K8s control plane is made up of three major components: the scheduler (kube-scheduler), the controller manager (kube-controller-manager) and the API server (kube-apiserver). The K8s control plane can run a single master node or can be replicated across multiple master nodes for high reliability.
Last mile	From telecommunications, the last mile corresponds to the final segment between the service provider and the user. Today, the last mile is often based on wireless and cellular communications.
Master node	The K8s node that holds the K8s control plane. The K8s master node holds configuration and state data and manages communication towards worker nodes (via the K8s API), to schedule containers efficiently.
Micro-service	An underlying component service of an application. Each micro-service in an application serves a specific service. An example is an application that integrates a PubSub broker; a database; an object detection application.
Migration	Process of transferring an ongoing application workload between two nodes.
Near Edge	near Edge is a definition tied to the Edge elements and services that are in the access/core regions of the network, i.e., between the far Edge and the Cloud data centres. The near Edge reflects the integration of ML to best support resource managements and to best orchestrate the applications to be served. An example of a near Edge architecture is the ETSI MEC 81. Near Edge hosts generic services. An example of a near Edge service is CDN.

Term	Definition
Network service	Set of operational network functionality needed to sustain user services. Examples of network services in CODECO are resource management, network exposure. For instance, Internet connectivity is a network service
Network infrastructure	Collection of links and of networking nodes that together enable data transmission between (Internet) users. The links connect the nodes together and are themselves built upon an underlying transmission network which physically pushes the message across the link.
Offloading	Offloading implies moving an application and its micro-services across different environments. Therefore, with offloading, the "old" environment, the application workload and its state are deleted and not simply made inactive; a copy of workload and of state, followed by eventual adaptation of state is done in the "new" environment.
Operator	From K8s. A Kubernetes operator watches a CR type and takes application-specific actions to make the current state match the desired state in that resource. Hence, an operator is a software extension that allows to encapsulate K8s application resources (i.e., Pods, Deployments, Daemon sets, Stateful sets, Jobs, Services, Configmaps, etc.) by creating a CR and a K8s controller. Operators track cluster events related to specific types of CRs. These CRs can track by default three types of events—add, update, and delete.
Pod	Pod follows also the K8s definition, being a logical wrapper entity for containers to be executed on a K8s cluster. This logical wrapper "holds" a group of one or more containers with shared storage and network resources, and a common namespace, providing a definition to run the containers. Pod may hold more than one container. A Pod is the unit of replication in a cluster.
Recipient of a service	"Recipient of the service" [2000/31/EC Art.2.d] any natural or legal person who, for professional ends or otherwise, uses an information society service, for the purposes of seeking information or making it accessible.
Replication	Replication implies that an application and its micro-services are copied across different locations, i.e., there are multiple replicas of the application in a system, some active, and some inactive. Replication requires a way to synchronize state across an "old" and a "new" environment where the application is deployed and implies that even inactive applications consume resources (at least storage).
Resources	A physical or virtual element of a global system. For instance, bandwidth, energy, data, devices, are examples of resources in CODECO.
Scheduler	A software-based entity that performs assignment of resources to perform specific tasks. The scheduler performs assignments based on a specific performance target, e.g., load-balancing, bounded latency, low jitter.
Session	Permanent or transient information exchange between two or more devices and/or users.
Stateful applications	Stateful applications keep state on clusters, and require that state (data, status of the application) to be kept.
Stateless applications	Stateless applications require no data storage to work.
User	A legal entity or individual using or requesting a publicly available electronic communications service for private or business purposes, without necessarily having subscribed to such service. In CODECO, a user can be i) a legal entity or individual (application developer) relying on the CODECO framework to setup and deploy an application across the Edge-Cloud continuum; ii) a legal entity or individual (CODECO service operator) relying on the CODECO framework to manage cluster configuration (setup) and runtime.
User service	A system that fulfills a need from an Internet end-user. For instance, VoIP and CDN are examples of user services.
Worker node	CODECO adopts the K8s worker node terminology. The workers are entities (K8s nodes) that run containerized micro-service. Each cluster has at least one worker node. Pods are assigned to worker nodes, where a local daemon

Term	Definition
	(Kubelet) manages the worker nodes life cycle. Kubelet is also the entry point to the K8s control plane.
Workload	An active micro-service and its state. A workload in CODECO is the minimum viable "unit" for migration, as it comprises a micro-service (e.g., storage), its state, and dependencies (e.g., networking resources).

Acknowledgements

We thank all CODECO Partners for the commitment and involvement in the development of Deliverable D9.

1 Introduction

The CODECO D9 deliverable describes the work that has been developed in the first six months of the CODECO *Work Package 2 (WP2)*, tasks 2.2 (*Technological Boundaries and Global Validation Design Aspects*), tasks 2.3 (*Open-source CODECO Ecosystem Design*), and task 2.4 (*CODECO architectural design*).

Specific goals that have been set in WP2 are: i) initial and clear definition of the use-cases and related business KPIs (T2.1, D8); ii) clear definition of the technological guidelines to be adopted by all partners in other WPs about tooling, benchmarking, analysis, code development; iii) development of good practices, licensing aspects, etc.; iv) development of the CODECO architectural design following open-source best practices.

This deliverable (D9) therefore covers items ii), iii) and iv) proposed for WP2.

1.1 Document Scope

D9 corresponds to an intermediate deliverable of WP2, covering work developed until month 6 of the project, and closing the first part of the work developed across tasks 2.2 to 2.4. D9 is supplemented by D10 (*CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design – final version*), due in month 18 (June 2024).

WP2 has two phases: the first phase, detailed in this deliverable, finishes in month 6 of the project (June 2023). The second phase runs from month 14 (Feb 2024) until month 18 (June 2024) and shall cover the final aspects of the architectural design of CODECO, integrating changes and customizations derived from the other WPs.

This deliverable provides:

- A summary of the CODECO vision, its global ecosystem, target stakeholders and main assets.
- A high-level description of the CODECO architecture, its components, and operation in one cluster, as well as operational considerations for operating CODECO on a federated clusters' environment, including a list of assumptions and requirements to be passed to the other WPs in CODECO.
- An overview on the CODECO key scientific contributions, and CODECO boundaries.
- Guidelines for the experiments and open-source assets development.

1.2 Dependencies

D9 has no dependencies to other deliverables. However, the companion deliverable D8 (Use-cases) provides additional input into the use-cases and application of the CODECO framework and its components in different environments and towards different vertical domains.

1.3 Document Structure

The Deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 1 introduces the overall deliverable scope and structure and briefly presents the CODECO ecosystem.
- Section 2 presents the CODECO high-level architecture and the CODECO components.
- Section 3 describes the CODECO contributions and technological guidelines in terms of research advancement.

- Section 4 addresses guidelines for global validation and experimentation.
- Section 5 addresses guidelines for the CODECO open-source output.
- Section 6 concludes the deliverable, presenting next steps.
- Annex I provides a list of initial metrics to be considered in CODECO.
- Annex II summarizes the initial CODECO interfaces.

1.4 The CODECO Ecosystem

CODECO affirms itself as a containerized application orchestration framework (TRL 4-5), independent and yet pluggable to *Kubernetes (K8s)*. The motivation to develop such framework relates with the current evolutionary aspects of the Internet and of an *Internet of Things (IoT)*. In this context, applications (and their components) need to be lightweight, highly portable, and mobile, to run anywhere and everywhere. Secondly, there is a need to handle large amounts of data often with very different features both in terms of computation (processing) and exchange (networking), including those with low latency demands. Thirdly, it is important to guarantee a smooth data flow, to allow for a smooth and secure integration end-to-end, across Edge-Cloud environments. Fourthly, real-time decision-making on where to compute and to store data must be supported.

As a cognitive and decentralised orchestration framework, CODECO embraces a next generation vision where data and services are stored and computed across the Internet whole-chain, in a holistic cooperation between Cloud and far Edge. Components of services, e.g., micro-services, reside in isolated, self-sufficient containers, which can be deployed and executed in any underlying environment. A flexible and secure networking infrastructure provides adaptable interconnection that adapt to the needs and the surrounding environment of the services being run. that integrates a unique, smart, and cross-layer orchestration between the decentralised data flow, computation, and networking services. The CODECO framework is established via the development of several assets, highlighted next, and explored across the ecosystem illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The CODECO ecosystem and target stakeholder groups.

The expected CODECO assets are:

- **A1: Open, cognitive toolkits and smart Apps**, integrating the elastic and advanced concepts to manage, in a smart and flexible way, containerized applications across Edge and Cloud (dynamic cluster and multi-cluster environment).
- **A2: A developer-oriented open-source software repository**, to be available in an early stage of the project, thus allowing for early exploitation of initial, advanced results and a better adaptation throughout the project lifetime.
- **A3: Training tools and events**, to support the development of services based on the CODECO framework.
- **A4: 6 Use-cases across 4 domains** (Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing, Mobility), to be deployed in operational environments.
- **A5: Research and Innovation Community Engagement Programme**, based on the different use-cases and including the different CODECO stakeholders.
- **A6: CODECO framework integration into the large-scale EdgeNet¹**, experimental infrastructure, to assist in the building of experimentation and novel concepts by the research community.

2 CODECO High-Level Architecture

This section covers the high-level specification of the CODECO architectural framework and provides input concerning the key computational aspects of each CODECO component. The architecture shall be periodically revised while the work is being developed across WP4-WP5; the **low-level design shall be provided in M18 of CODECO**.

To assist in the understanding of the overall components, the section starts with an overview on the architectural design methodology, and then provides a high-level perspective into the CODECO framework, then covering the high-level definition of each component, followed by examples for the CODECO operation across one cluster and federated clusters.

2.1 Architectural Design Methodology

To design the CODECO architecture, the used methodology considered the following steps, as illustrated in Figure 2:

- **Pre-design**: the starting point has been the design of CODECO presented in the Grant Agreement. This design took into consideration a thorough analysis of related work, and into key challenges derived from the CODECO use-cases (T2.1), as well as into an analysis concerning initial tooling to be considered (T2.3) and component brainstorming developed in WP3.
- **System level design of each component**: the different Partners have provided, based on the initial reading of each component, a proposed design with specific sub-services, focusing on the following aspects:
 - **Generic description**, covering the overall operation and computational aspects associated with the component, including a high-level functional scheme of the component.
 - **Key technologies**, covering open-source solutions expected to be used in the next phase of component specification and implementation.
 - **Sub-component description**.

¹ <https://edge-net.org/>

- **Interfaces** between sub-components, and towards other CODECO components.
- **Summary of the expected operation for one cluster and multiple clusters.**
- **List of requirements**, following the IETF principles: The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in IETF RFC 2119 [2].
- **Domain level design of the overarching architecture.** The Partners have addressed, based on the individual design of each component, a proposed high-level design for the CODECO architecture.
- Refinement of components and of the overall architecture, based on the application to different use-cases.

Figure 2: High-level architectural design methodology.

2.2 Terminology, K8s, and the Edge-Cloud Continuum

The terminology used in this deliverable is provided the “*List of Definitions*”. Furthermore, for the sake of readability, this sub-section briefly explains the overall K8s operation and provides a sub-set of the terms related with dynamic container orchestration [8], to assist the reader in getting a faster grasp of the proposed architecture.

An **application** is considered to consist of multiple **micro-services** that can be run independently based on container technology, such as Docker. This is named containerized micro-service, or containerized application. **Application workload** refers therefore to the containerized micro-services, namely, binary system, data, state, i.e., a set of global variables defined in the micro-services and required at run-time. A containerized application therefore consists of one or several containerized micro-services which are interconnected via specific interfacing policies. The different micro-services may be deployed across different **nodes**, i.e., different cyber-physical systems (including virtual machines). To scale the application, allowing to meet specific requirements, e.g., bounded latency, it is feasible to consider **migration** strategies, e.g., transparent **replication** or **offloading**, also known as **relocation**. Applications supported in this process can be stateless or stateful. Stateless applications require no data storage to work. An example is a Web search. Stateful applications keep state on clusters, and require that state (data, status of the application) to be kept and eventually found.

Edge, Cloud definitions, including the notions of **far Edge/near Edge** follow the line of thought being driven in the European initiatives EUCEI² and former *Next Generation IoT (NGIoT)*³ and, the vision for smart, decentralised Edge-Cloud environments for IoT applications [1].

Container follows the K8s definition, where it is a package with the overall settings (workload, state, data) to allow execution of an application in an independent way and logically run in a Pod.

A **Pod** follows also the K8s definition, being a logical wrapper entity for containers to be executed on a K8s cluster. This logical wrapper "holds" a group of one or more containers with shared storage and network resources, and a common namespace, providing a definition to run the containers. Hence, a Pod is the unit of replication in a cluster. A (K8s) **cluster** corresponds to the logical environment where Pods run in a way that has been orchestrated by a human operator (the **user**).

The high-level operation of K8s is illustrated in Figure 3. A K8s cluster consists of multiple **worker nodes**, where Pods are scheduled to, and a **master node**, which corresponds to the **K8s control plane**. K8s nodes run in Edge-Cloud **nodes**, i.e., cyber-physical systems.

Figure 3: K8s high-level operation, 1 cluster, roles in the master and worker nodes.

The master node (control plane) stores configuration and data and manages worker nodes and Pods in a cluster. For this, the master node integrates **etcd**, a key-value internal database, which keeps the configuration of a cluster, is based on the Raft consensus protocol [3], and which stores/manages, among other K8s resources, the **K8s Custom Resource Definitions, CRDs**; the API server (**K8s API** or **kube-apiserver**); **scheduler**; **controller-manager**. The K8s API is the control plane front-end component.

2 <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

3 <https://www.ngiot.eu/>

The **controller** is the control-plane component (control loop) that runs processes which are continuously checking the state of the cluster and comparing them to the desired state in etcd, then being able to make or to request changes when required. The controller usually performs re-scheduling based on actions provided by the API server, but it can also execute the action itself. For example, a controller can scale nodes in a cluster. When the desired state is updated, the controllers will detect the mismatch and try to bring the cluster state to the desired one. CODECO counts with specific controllers as shall be explained in sub-section 2.4.

The desired state of a cluster is defined by a **user** via the API server. In CODECO, a user is i) an **application developer (user DEV)**, willing to deploy an application across Edge-Cloud; ii) a K8s infrastructure manager (**user MGR**), willing to automate the configuration, deployment, and management of clusters.

In K8s, the API server receives the cluster configuration and application requirements from the user, storing them in a K8s format (**CRDs**) based on YAML⁴, in etcd. CRDs provide a definition to **Custom Resources (CRs)**, listing out all the configuration available to users.

A K8s **operator** (a combination of CRs and a custom controller) is a software extension that provides support to package, deploy, and manage K8s resources. The operator configuration is provided in a CRD to the user; the operator is therefore associated with a CRD/CR. The operator watches the CR and takes resource-specific actions to make the current state match the desired state in that resource.

A scheduler (in the case of K8s, kube-scheduler; in the case of CODECO, SWM-scheduler) handles the Pod to Node matching decisions, so that **kubelet** on the worker nodes can then run the Pods. Kubelet is the entry point from/to the K8s control plane. We also highlight that currently K8s provides replication support, and not offloading support, an aspect that we expect to further explore in CODECO, to best support new challenges, such as node mobility.

For the matching, K8s relies on a filtering and scoring approach. On a first phase (**filtering**), the scheduler checks which nodes can meet the scheduling requirements. These nodes are named **feasible nodes**. On a second phase (**scoring**), the scheduler ranks the feasible nodes for the "best" Pod deployment, by calculating scheduling priorities, also defined in the desired state. As shall be seen in section 2.4.3 (SWM), CODECO follows a different approach to perform the Pod-Node matching, allowing more flexibility and providing the basis to consider a matching that suits better the application requirements.

The applications across Edge-Cloud are therefore orchestrated via multiple clusters, where an Edge environment, or an Edge-Cloud environment may be inside a single cluster (e.g., if under the operation of a same service provider) or of multiple clusters (e.g., across multi-domain environments). We highlight here that an Edge node is different from a K8s node. A K8s node may (or not) reside on an Edge node.

2.3 Framework Architecture

Next generation Internet of applications are today based on micro-service architectures, where their components are usually containerized. The deployment of applications across Edge-Cloud is managed via container orchestrators such as K8s, tools that provide partial automated support to the setup and lifecycle management of containerized applications.

⁴ <https://yaml.org/>

Some of the tasks handled by orchestrators include configuration and scheduling as well as provisioning of containers; checking availability of containers; scaling the system to balance application workloads across the overall infrastructure; allocating resources to the different containers and monitoring their health; enabling the communication exchange between containers.

The initial design of container orchestrators contemplated a Cloud-based deployment. However, with the increasing move of data storage, processing and analysis to the so-called *far Edge*, applications and their micro-services can be scattered across mobile, often constrained environments. CODECO and its components, illustrated in Figure 4, is a software-based orchestration framework interoperable with K8s aims at providing support to a next generation of container orchestrators which can adapt and learn, developing a proper reaction and adaptation to diverse requirements coming from the data, from the application, from the system, from the network and: from the end-user.

For this purpose, and as detailed in the GA, Annex II (DoA), also taking into consideration the proposed CODECO use-cases (rf. to the CODECO Deliverable D8), CODECO proposes to focus on the following aspects which are further technologically debated in section 4.1 (CODECO contributions):

- **Automated configuration**, focusing on supporting application setup and application runtime across Edge-Cloud, by taking into consideration compute, network, and data aspects. The key aspects of this contribution shall be integrated into the CODECO *Advanced Configuration and Management (ACM)* component, coordinated by Partner RedHat (RHT) (rf. to section 2.4.1).
- **Data as a resource**. CODECO addresses, via its Metadata Manager (MDM) component (rf. to section 2.4.2), data as a resource in the sense that available snapshots from the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure, integrating different perspectives (application, user, system, data, network) at different instants of the CODECO operational workflow can be provided to different CODECO components, to assist in detecting relevant changes.
- **Dynamic scheduling and workload migration**. Supported by the CODECO component *Scheduling and Workload Migration (SWM)*, CODECO builds on the concept of seamless computing (Partner Siemens) integrating novel QoS models that consider data-network-computation requirements to provide a best match between applications and available infrastructure (nodes, their computational and data properties, as well as network nodes and links), and to schedule and re-schedule application workloads across single cluster and federated cluster environments, considering application and user requirements. The SWM component (rf. to section 2.4.3) performs informed decisions on scheduling/re-scheduling and migration, which take into consideration long-term behaviour and learning of such behaviour.
- **Context-awareness and privacy preserving decentralised learning**. CODECO relies on context-awareness to be able to achieve a joint data-network-compute orchestration, and on privacy-preserving decentralised learning and inference to best support readjustment of aspects such as the processing capability, computational resources, networking resources and interconnections in real-time. Context-awareness (coordinated by Partner fortiss, FOR) and decentralised learning (coordinated by partner I2CAT) are part of the CODECO PDLC component (rf. to section 2.4.4).
- **Infrastructure adaptation based on a cross-layer data-compute-network approach**. Via the CODECO *Network Management and Adaptation component (NetMA)*, CODECO assists in adapting not just computational (node resources) but also the networking infrastructure interconnecting such nodes, having as starting point for the exposure of metadata within 1 cluster and across federated clusters the ALTO protocol [4] (Partner

Telefonica, TID), which will be considered for decentralised environments, from far Edge to Cloud. Rf. to section 2.4.5 for the description of NetMA.

Figure 4: The CODECO K8s framework and its components.

The overall CODECO architecture is illustrated in Figure 5, considering as starting point the CODECO operation within a single cluster deployment (M1-M18 of CODECO). The different CODECO components are further detailed in sub-section 2.4. Each component description comprises:

- High-level specification of operation.
- Key technologies serving as basis for the deployment of the component.
- Description of sub-components, and interfaces.
- Generic operation within one cluster.
- Considerations towards federated clusters, to be considered during the second phase of the development of CODECO (M18-M36).

Each CODECO component is expected to be built as one or several independent (dockerized) micro-services.

For the representation provided in Figure 5 and subsequent component descriptions, a few considerations are here summarized to assist the reader of this deliverable:

- I-comp1-comp2-X describes components from CODECO component 1 to CODECO component 2. For instance, I-MDM-PDLC-1 means that an interface from MDM to PDLC of type *Input*, *Output*, or *bi-directional* is being conceived.
- The high-level interfaces between CODECO components are illustrated in strong, dashed green lines.
- Internal interfaces between sub-components are represented via light, dashed, blue lines.
- Interfaces to external entities, e.g., user, non-K8s systems are represented via a black, solid line.
- Interfaces are described per component in the next sub-sections, and available as a list in Annex II of this deliverable.

Figure 5: CODECO high-level architecture.

2.3.1 CODECO Workflow Example, One Cluster

This sub-section aims at providing the reader with enough detail to later understand the way the CODECO components are being specified and implemented. The description relies on Figure 5 (CODECO architecture).

2.3.1.1 Creating an Application Deployment with CODECO

Bob (representing in this example a user DEV) is a developer wanting to deploy an application composed of multiple micro-services (multiple docker images) across far Edge-Cloud. For this purpose, Bob has installed the open-source CODECO framework, available via the ECL CODECO GitLab⁵, and its dependencies.

ACM provides Bob, with an automated way to dimension the cluster, e.g., selection of nodes, cluster naming, tagging. Bob is also provided with the CODECO application workflow model (via a dashboard GUI or via specific YAML files), where Bob shall define specific application requirements, e.g., levels of security, latency, level of reliability. Internally, ACM builds the *CODECO Application Model* and makes it accessible to all CODECO components.

ACM handles also the full K8s setup (e.g., namespace, databases, secrets), providing the information, if required, to other K8s components. For instance, meta-data information, schema, can be passed to MDM (I-ACM-MDM-2). Application requirements derived from the CODECO Application Model, e.g., dedicated CPU, required bandwidth, are made accessible to SWM (I-ACM-SWM-1) and to PDLC (I-ACM-PDLC-1), for instance.

The exposure of requirements and application/user information triggers also the operation of each CODECO component. PDLC establishes the processes to activate the sensing and (decentralised learning) processes for the cluster. SWM performs a request to PDLC to obtain the initial weights to consider on the scheduling optimization (I-PDLC-SWM-1).

NetMA triggers the definition of the networking overlay once it receives the initial deployment from SWM (I-SWM-NET-1).

After activation, PDLC regularly obtains, via available CRs/CRDS (I-ACM-PDLC-1,2), metadata provided by MDM (data metrics), ACM (user aspects and application constrains, i.e., the CODECO Application Model), NetMA (network metrics); performs an initial multi-level objective estimation based on the user selected target profiles, and stores the output on a PDLC CRD, making it available to ACM, which may trigger adjustments to the initial setup process.

In parallel, three components start the monitoring of different metrics. NetMA captures networking metrics at a node, link, and path level, exposing such information via specific CRs, which shall be accessible by all components, and used by PDLC and ACM.

Similarly, MDM captures data aspects (e.g., data compliance), generating a knowledge graph and providing the output also as an MDM CR.

ACM captures user preferences and eventually behaviour, which may be beneficial for adapting the overall K8s infrastructure at a later stage.

In this way, CODECO is integrating into the K8s deployment process the data-compute-network approach of CODECO.

2.3.1.2 CODECO Support during Cluster Runtime

Once the setup is complete, CODECO enters the cluster management phase (application runtime support), targeting user MGR. During this phase the proposed application (CODECO Application Workload) has been setup and is running across several containers (1 cluster), 1

⁵ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

or multiple Pods per worker node. PDLC periodically obtains data from MDM (I-MDM-PDLC-1); from NetMA and ACM (I-ACM-PDLC-1), and feedback from SWM concerning the application workload placement (I-SWM-PDLC-1). Based on this, PDLC periodically assesses the proposed system performance target objectives (e.g., greenness level, service latency) which have been provided by Bob during the application setup, providing via a CR a cost combination per infrastructure element (I-PDLC-ACM-2). If there is the need for cross-layer redistribution of the application workload, this step triggers a request by ACM to all CODECO components. In this case, PDLC passes a behaviour estimation to SWM (I-PDLC-SWM-2) via a specific CR; SWM starts the process of workload placement. Once the process is completed, SWM passes feedback to PDLC (I-SWM-PDLC-1). This will not be an explicit interface; instead, the feedback is provided via specific SWM CRs (currently, ApplicationGroup, Application, AssignmentPlan, further detailed in section 2.4.3). Feedback will be passed to the user (Anne, User MGR), via the Prometheus CODECO monitoring architecture (rf. to section 2.4.1).

2.3.2 CODECO Workflow Example, Federated Clusters

While the operation of CODECO shall only be defined during the second phase of CODECO (M18-M36), this sub-section provides an initial perspective on how CODECO shall facilitate federated clusters deployment.

2.3.2.1 Creating an Application Deployment with CODECO

CODECO oversees operations in multi-cluster environments by allowing the federated set of clusters to operate as a single, self-organizing entity. In other words, CODECO proposes mechanisms to sustain a self-organizing behaviour of multi-cluster environments, where each cluster only has partial information of the full multi-cluster system. For this purpose, during the federated cluster system setup, ACM builds upon its basic behaviour and further provides the users in each cluster with a specific sub-set of well-defined features (pre-conditions, to be defined and implemented in WP4, T4.1). Based on this subset of information and on a semantic abstraction model of the clusters, the CODECO components that capture specific metrics (data, user, application, network), shall now handle a new level of complexity.

For instance, MDM shall expose data of each cluster and must also handle the multi-cluster data workflow deployment. NetMA shall expose the capabilities and services/service policies of each cluster in a way that allows each cluster to independently adapt (WP4, T4.1); and triggers the required operations to handle interconnections across multi-cluster domains.

During the federated cluster management phase, there are services running across multi-cluster domains, being supported by CODECO. PDLC shall therefore consider a hybrid federated learning approach or a decentralised learning approach (an example is swarm learning) to support readjustment of each cluster and of the overall system. PDLC still continuously assesses, in each cluster the proposed objectives (e.g., greenness level, service latency); it interacts with the ACM on the need to perform the required readjustment, e.g., adding more nodes. (Re-) distribution of the workload follows the same line of thought as in the CODECO basic operation, being handled by the SWM. What changes is that such readjustment, as well as initial or subsequent scheduling and deployment of applications, is performed independently on each cluster, but considering the whole multi-cluster environment as a single system.

2.4 High-level Specification of CODECO Components

This section provides an overview concerning the CODECO components initial specification based on the methodology described in section 2.1 and derived from the initial six months of the project. The aim is to describe the components with enough level of detail, to best guide the CODECO specification and implementation work in WP3 and WP4. The components specification and the overall CODECO architecture will be further refined and adapted on a later stage of the project, between M14 and M36.

2.4.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management

2.4.1.1 Description

ACM provides methodologies and tools that support the CODECO automatic configuration, regarding application setup and deployment across Edge-Cloud, for single and multi-cluster environments. ACM is based on the *Open Cluster Management (OCM)*⁶ community driven project which is the upstream project for Red Hat *Advanced Cluster Management*⁷. The CODECO ACM component contemplates the CODECO integration into embedded and small footprint nodes; the development of K8s operators (and if required, additional semantic interfaces) that extend the ACM operation towards the other CODECO components; automated configuration and user interfacing, to support operations across multi-cluster (federated clusters) in a way that is transparent to the user; autoscaling.

ACM addresses security focusing on attack mitigation and detection across multi-cluster (distributed environments).

For this purpose, CODECO ACM operation considers three main categories of aspects that address the integration of CODECO across the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure:

- **Integration points between users and applications.** Mechanisms for users (e.g., user DEV) to control and change configuration of the applications to be run across the Edge-Cloud continuum.
- **CODECO configuration.** A specific user request during application deployment setup or application runtime implies activation and eventual configuration of CODECO components, e.g., NetMA, PDLC. This can be done, for instance, by enhancing the K8s API with CRDs and adding operators to monitor the changes in the CRs, reacting accordingly. The current architectural design cannot yet (M6) fully foresee all interactions between CODECO components. However, based on the initial design presented in this deliverable, it is foreseen that the main interfacing aspects between components can be covered via CRD/CRs and CODECO operators.
- **Cluster/federated cluster configuration.** The user in this case is a user MGT, handling the K8s infrastructure. A specific change to the CODECO configuration (for instance, increase or decrease in the application workload due to dataset changes) may imply the need to install, configure (for example, policy configuration, CODECO components deployments), or reconfigure a cluster.

Figure 2 shows the different interaction points between ACM and the other CODECO components. Since ACM is the integration point towards the user, it is also in charge of the system installation - the user can install the CODECO framework by installing the CODECO meta-operator (which is part of ACM), where this process triggers the installation of the entire

6 <https://open-cluster-management.io/>

7 <https://www.redhat.com/en/technologies/management/advanced-cluster-management>

CODECO system on the cluster to be managed and configured. In addition, there may be the explicit need to export more information from the CODECO system to the cluster control plane and towards the users. This task also falls under the ACM umbrella.

At the bottom (yellow colour) is the CODECO interface, and at the top (blue colour) the various K8s functionalities that are hidden from the CODECO user. These functionalities are, however, available for CODECO platform developers. Since the CODECO meta-operator is the only operator exposed towards the users, it is therefore in charge of the entire CODECO system installation, including the installation of all its components and their operators (MDM, PDLC, SWM and NetMA).

Figure 6: ACM interaction points to CODECO components and external systems and users.

Additional architecture options and notes, which are currently not decided and therefore also not represented in Figure 2:

- For CODECO internal integration (integration between CODECO components) we may provide direct APIs (using technology such as REST/HTTP) for scenarios which are not suited well for CRD based APIs (for example, retrieving temporal or complex datasets). Please refer to the MDM component for examples on the need of such interfaces.
- If there is a need to integrate CODECO with a non-k8s system, we may need to provide some kind of gateway sub-component that translates between external API calls (such as REST/HTTP) and CODECO K8s-based APIs.
- Each CODECO component may have more than one CR that it controls, and more than a single operator. This will be determined later in the detailed design process and can change during the development process.
- CODECO components can access other components CRs directly, but CODECO users will not have the privileges for directly accessing CODECO component CRs (blue colour).

2.4.1.2 Key Technologies

- Multi-cluster centralized management based on OCM (to be developed during the second phase of CODECO, M18-M36).
- K8s API extensions via CRD/CRs and respective operators.
- Prometheus⁸ and exporters such as the *Kubernetes-based Efficient Power Level Exporter*, *Kepler*⁹, as well as new Prometheus operators to support new monitoring plugins provided in the different CODECO components, supporting the integration of new metrics in K8s (rf. To PDLC-CA, section 2.4.4.).
- Knative¹⁰ to support serverless deployment of containerized applications across Edge-Cloud.
- Lightweight K8s distribution solutions such as K3s¹¹, Microshift¹², for far Edge integration.
- Integration with non-K8s far Edge nodes based on solutions such as Flotta¹³.
- Secure onboarding of devices, considering *Fast Identity Online (FIDO)* and *Trusted Execution Environments (TEE)* approaches.
- Fast provisioning of K8s clusters on remote worker nodes via solutions such as Hypershift¹⁴.
- Ansible¹⁵, to support the automated deployment of CODECO.

2.4.1.3 Sub-components

ACM uses existing open-source technologies and will need to extend some of these technologies to support CODECO components and APIs. It is envisioned that ACM will rely on the initially proposed technologies as detailed in section 2.4.1.2. The ACM initial sub-components, illustrated in Figure 7, are:

- **OCM:** This sub-component is the basis for ACM and is used to enable end-to-end visibility and control across K8s clusters. It will be used to provide the main ACM functionality and extended to provide special support and visibility of the CODECO components.
- **K8s API extensibility and CRD/CRs.** This is a mechanism that is provided by K8s to extend its functionality and provide native access to new components. We are going to utilize this mechanism to provide native K8s APIs to the CODECO framework thus making the interaction with the CODECO components seamless and making the CODECO framework K8s native.
- **Monitoring: new metrics integrated into Prometheus:** Different CODECO components (ACM, NetMA, MDM) collect parameters that shall assist in a more flexible schedule, with compute, network, and data awareness. The CODECO components collecting input shall monitor specific parameters and provide these in CRD/CRs. The CODECO component PDLC and its sub-component PDLC-CA (rf. to section 2.4.4) shall assist in the development of new metrics derived from the collected parameters. ACM monitoring shall therefore be a sub-component that shall articulate the monitoring across the different

8 <https://prometheus.io/>

9 <https://sustainable-computing.io/>

10 <https://knative.dev>

11 <https://k3s.io/>

12 <https://github.com/openshift/microshift>

13 <https://project-flotta.io/>

14 <https://github.com/openshift/hypershift>

15 <https://www.ansible.com/>

components and propose an integration into Prometheus. The new CODECO CRDs can be extended to, among other functionalities, specify how groups of K8s services or Pods should be monitored or to specify scrape configurations to be added to Prometheus. Built in K8s metrics can also be enhanced by gathering more information with the use of node exporters or eBPF hooks, like Kepler that relies on eBPF to probe energy-related system stats and exports them as Prometheus metrics. The proposed CODECO sub-component monitoring architecture is illustrated in Figure 8.

- **Automated configuration via Knative and Ansible.** We will use Knative when we need scalable stateless functions that can be easily scaled-out and scaled-in upon load change. This is usually a requirement for many stream processing and event-driven functions. Ansible shall be used to support the automation of cluster configuration and CODECO deployment tasks in ACM.
- **Control plane for independent/isolated clusters** – There are multiple open-source technologies that handle this problem (for example, KCP¹⁶) and it is yet to be decided which technology to use for this problem. Here, the aim is to consider mobile environments where intermittent connectivity may prevent the registration of a cluster to the OCM Hub. An example relates with the use of clusters involving mobile devices, such as cars (rf. to D8 use-cases. P2), or Automated Guided Vehicles (rf. To D8 use-cases, P5).
- **Far Edge integration,** via lightweight K8s distributions. CODECO addresses the support of clusters involving embedded devices at the far Edge, potentially mobile. Hence, ACM considers the integration and interoperability to handle lightweight support via solutions such as K3s, Microshift.
- **Integration towards non-K8s systems.** ACM supports connectivity towards non-k8s nodes via Flotta, to provide the connection of containerized workload to other K8s clusters.
- **Secure deployment.** The secure onboarding of new cyber-physical systems at the Edge is handled via ACM, based on tools such as FIDO and TEE.
- **Hierarchical control plane.** Via Hypershift, ACM supports a separation of the control plane into a centralized cluster (Cloud or Edge) and considering that remote worker nodes are being deployed at the Edge.

Figure 7: ACM and its sub-components, high-level specification.

¹⁶<https://github.com/kcp-dev/kcp#-kcp>

Figure 8: CODECO monitoring architecture.

2.4.1.4 Interfaces

As has been explained in section 2.4.1.1, ACM is the single-entry point in CODECO to the users, thus interacting directly with K8s and non-K8s systems. The current interfaces of ACM to other components, identified in Figure 7 are summarized in Table 1. The full set of interfaces between ACM and the other CODECO components are based on the extensibility of K8s APIs and will be defined when the exact integration points are finalized.

Table 1: ACM interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-ACM-PROM	Integration of the CODECO metrics into Prometheus	CRD	Bi-directional
I-ACM-MDM-1	Data collection from CRDs of other components, to be used in the MDM integration of the CODECO MDM operator.	CRD	Bi-directional
I-ACM-MDM-2	Integration of additional data types	To be defined	Input
I-ACM-PDLC-1	Integration of CA derived metrics into Prometheus	CRD	Input
I-ACM-PDLC-2	Use of CRDs from other components by PDLC	CRD	Output
I-ACM-NET-1	Integration of the NetMA CRD/CR(s) and respective operator(s)	CRD	Input
I-ACM-SWM-1	Integration of the SWM controller-manager (CRD/CR(s) via K8s API)	CR via K8s API (REST)	Bi-directional

Once the integration points (APIs) of the CODECO components are known, we will define together the CRDs and the behaviour upon changes in the CRDs and build operators that react to the changes in the CRs. When all this is done, the APIs can be invoked by sending YAML that describes the custom resource to the appropriate K8s endpoint.

From a technical perspective the APIs represent the lifecycle of the CRs and follow the lifecycle pattern, these are K8s APIs which have the following verbs on resources:

- Create
- Delete
- Modify
- Verify

Upon calling one of these APIs on a CR, the control is sent to the operator that manages this type of resource and this operator is responsible for reacting to the change.

Obviously, **the methodology listed above is not appropriate for all interfaces**, it is the desired methodology for configuration changes and hence for most of the CODECO components APIs. In some cases, applications (or even components) may want to react to events or to data streams and they can use appropriate tools for these types of interfaces, this will be decided based on the requirements from each interface. For platform configuration, however, the K8s pattern of resource changes is highly recommended and will be used in most cases¹⁷.

2.4.1.5 Generic Operation for One Cluster

As has been explained, ACM relies on OCM (the upstream version of the RHT project ACM), which provides benefits for federated clusters. While within a cluster, OCM is not required (as OKD¹⁸ is enough), having said that, since OCM is going to be the entry point to the CODECO platform, and considerable work will be needed for customizing it for CODECO we don't see a value in creating a single cluster solution with OKD and a multi-cluster solution with OCM, so we will start with OCM even for a single cluster.

2.4.1.6 Considerations for Federated Clusters

The design of development of ACM is purposely based on OCM for one cluster, to ease the adaptation across federated clusters. All clusters will be added to the OCM managed clusters list and will be managed by the existing OCM.

2.4.2 MDM: Metadata Manager

2.4.2.1 Description

The CODECO MDM component aims at supporting real-time Edge applications and in achieving a higher degree of efficiency in Cloud-Edge operations. The MDM is a new system that integrates 3 novel aspects: i) a semantic data catalogue including a rich set of metadata providing a complete cross-domain view of data and the characteristics of the data (e.g., schema, lineage, classification); ii) data discovery, aiming at enriching the collected metadata, including input provided by other CODECO components (via CRDs) and learnings derived from the multi-cluster operation; iii) data orchestration support, to assist CODECO in making orchestration decisions that are cognizant of data constraints (e.g., performance issues if there are frequent accesses to remote data or compliance issues that may preclude copying data).

The MDM catalogue information encompasses attributes and properties such as data source, semantic description, classification, identification; data structure (e.g., data type, schema); application-specific information (e.g., data analysis, curation aspects); network specific information (e.g., access latency, bandwidth). The catalogue is populated continuously, based on a pull model whenever new datasets are created. It is therefore populated via PDLC, directly via data-sources, or via the ACM (user input). MDM keeps track of the meta-data and provides a common platform where all metadata (multi-cluster) can be shared across multiple domains. MDM interacts also with other catalogues, providing a starting point for the interconnection with the Gaia-X service catalogue composition model and architecture, to ensure compliance and broader usage.

The CODECO MDM component collects, links, and enriches metadata related with the applications to be deployed across Edge-Cloud. This metadata assists in better characterizing

¹⁷ More information on extending the k8s APIs with CRDs can be found in <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/extend-kubernetes/custom-resources/custom-resource-definitions/>

¹⁸ <https://www.okd.io/>

the application deployment across Edge-Cloud. MDM is therefore a CODECO component that acts as a gateway between the data world (data workflow) and the K8s infrastructure (compute).

Example entities in a K8s and CODECO setting include “pods”, “deployments”, “namespaces”, “worker nodes”, as well as “datastore”, “file”, “s3 bucket”, etc. Relationships are also typed and connect exactly two entities. Relationships have a direction. For example, the relationship “contains” may be used to express that a namespace contains a set of pods.

MDM and its sub-components are illustrated in Figure 9. MDM collects metadata from any “native system” that has information on the data, including data stores, catalogues, pipelines that copy and transform data, use-case specific functions that analyse the data, or any other relevant system. For this purpose, MDM relies on **connector interfaces** for each specific data type (I-MDM-E-1).

Figure 9: MDM high-level specification.

An MDM connector interfaces to a native data system or CRD, and pushes metadata into a knowledge graph through the native (internal) MDM API. By adding new connectors or expanding the graph model, the system can be extended to collect any required metadata. MDM is event-based, relying on Apache Kafka¹⁹. MDM relies on the Kafka event queue, a log of metadata events that occur for an Edge-Cloud setting managed with CODECO. Events describe changes that have happened and correspond to insert/update/delete of metadata entities and relationships.

MDM materializes (subsets of) the event queue in the knowledge graph to meet the needs of other CODECO components.

2.4.2.2 Key Technologies

The MDM metadata collection is materialized in data systems that make it convenient to manage and exploit the metadata. The key technologies used in the current MDM implementation include:

- **Apache Kafka:** Distributed event store and stream processing.
- **Apache ZooKeeper**²⁰, for the overall Kafka management and coordination (e.g., configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization).

¹⁹ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

²⁰ <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>

- **Neo4j, MariaDB, or PostgreSQL**, for holding the metadata. Depending on the data expected data volume and query requirements, either a graphDB or a relational database will be used.

2.4.2.3 Sub-components

The sub-components represented in Figure 9 are dockerized.

2.4.2.3.1 MDM API

The MDM API is based on OpenAPI REST (OAS REST API) and integrates four endpoint groups, as illustrated in Figure 10:

- **Producer** which is the endpoint for connectors writing to the MDM.
- **Events** which is the endpoint to get events from MDM.
- **Projection** gets information by querying the data projection. Initially this would allow for Cypher queries to be performed on the knowledge graph. If because of the experience gained with partners the set of queries required for the CODECO operation can be defined in a closed set, they can be incorporated to this API at a later stage.
- **MDM** is the system information endpoint for getting status and resets or other system relevance functions.

All endpoints are protected and authorized usage enabled.

Method	Endpoint	Description
Producer		
POST	/producer	send data to kafka
Projection		
GET	/graph/entity/type	get list of entity types
POST	/graph/entity/type/{entitytype}	get list of entities
GET	/graph/entity/attributes/{entitytype}	get list of all possible attributes of the entity
GET	/graph/path/{edf_id}	get graph node relation by hops
POST	/graph/cypher	execute a read only cypher and get the result
MDM		
GET	/mdm	get system info
GET	/mdm/state	get MDM system state
DELETE	/mdm/clean	deleta all Projection and data
Events		
GET	/events/sse	ServerSideEvent

Figure 10: MDM API and its endpoints.

2.4.2.3.2 Event Data Model

Connectors send metadata to MDM in the form of events. Events are structured JSON documents. An event contains the following elements:

1. The event type, either “insert” or “delete”.
2. An identifier that uniquely identifies the connector that issued the event.
3. A timestamp.
4. The payload, i.e., the metadata.

Metadata is sent as entities and relationships. MDM imposes a basic structure on both entities and relationships to ensure that metadata can be stored as a graph. Entities must have a globally unique identifier and a type. It is the task of the connector to assign these. In addition, entities contain arbitrary numbers of attributes. The mandatory elements of a relationship are source and target entity identifier as well as a type. Relationships do not carry attributes. MDM does not define or enforce a static data model. Instead, the graph data model is defined by the structure of the entities and relationships that are inserted into MDM. MDM expects a set of rules to be followed by entities and relationships:

- Connectors assign a universally unique identifier to each entity that they insert. The UUID is deterministically computed from properties of the entity. For example, the UUID of an entity representing a Kubernetes Pod is computed using the cluster ID, the namespace, and the Pod name.
- Connectors “own” the entities that they insert. A connector that inserts an entity has the rights to update and remove it again.
- Connectors cannot change or delete entities that have been inserted by other connectors.
- Connectors use a consistent method for computing the entity IDs. This enables connectors to integrate the entities that they produce into the graph by creating relationships to existing entities.
- A relationship defines how an entity is related to another entity. The connector computes the relationships’ endpoint IDs using the same deterministic method that is used for computing the entity IDs.
- Connectors own the relationships that they insert. A connector has the right to remove its own relationships again. Since relationships do not have properties, they cannot be changed.
- Connectors cannot overwrite relationships that have been inserted by other connectors.

A simplistic model for representing Pods running in a K8s cluster consists of a cluster entity²¹, a Pod entity, and a runs relationship. This model is specified using JSON schema. The cluster entity type with a minimalistic set of attributes:

```
{
  "$id": "urn:org.codeco.mdm.model:cluster:1.0.0",
  "$schema": "https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/schema",
  "description": "A kubernetes cluster",
  "type": "object",
  "required": ["json_schema_ref", "edf_id", "name", "url"],
  "properties": {
    "json_schema_ref": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "The id of the JSON schema used to encode the payload."
    },
    "edf_id": {
```

21 Rf. to the Apache Kafka K8 operator Strimzi, used to run Apache Kafka on a K8s cluster.

```
"description": "Unique identifier of the entity.",  
"type": "string",  
"format": "uuid"  
},  
"name": {"type": "string", "description": "The (human readable) name of the cluster" },  
"description": {"type": "string", "description": "A description of the entity. May be empty." },  
"url": {  
"type": "string",  
"description": "URL that is used to locate this entity. May be empty."  
},  
"country_code": {  
"type": "string",  
"description": "ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 two letter code"  
}  
}  
}
```

Every entity type contains at least the **json_schema_ref** and the **edf_id** attributes. It is also recommended that every entity contains a name. The rest of the attributes can be defined freely. Likewise, a K8s Pod could be defined as:

```
{  
"$id": "urn:org.codeco.mdm.model:Pod:1.0.0",  
"$schema": "https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/schema",  
"description": "A kubernetes Pod",  
"type": "object",  
"required": ["json_schema_ref", "edf_id", "name"],  
"properties": {  
"json_schema_ref": {  
"type": "string",  
"description": "The id of the JSON schema used to encode the payload."  
},  
"edf_id": {  
"description": "Unique identifier of the entity.",  
"type": "string",  
"format": "uuid"  
},  
"name": {  
"type": "string",  
"description": "The (human readable) name of the Pod"  
},  
"description": {  
"type": "string",  
"default": null,  
"description": "A description of the entity. May be empty."  
},  
"identifier": {  
"type": "string",  
"default": null,  
"description": "Name or other identifier of the Pod. May be empty."  
}  
}  
}
```

Finally, a relationship is used to indicate that the cluster runs a specific Pod:

```
{  
"$id": "urn:org.codeco.mdm.model:runs:1.0.0",  
"$schema": "https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/schema",  
"description": "A runs relationship.",  
"type": "object",  
"unevaluatedProperties": false,  
"properties": {  
"json_schema_ref": {
```



```

"type": "string",
"description": "The id of the JSON schema used to encode the payload."
},
"from_edf_id": {
"description": "Reference to the source entity of this relationship.",
"type": "string", "format": "uuid"
},
"to_edf_id": {
"description": "Reference to the target entity of this relationship.",
"type": "string", "format": "uuid"
}
},
"required": [ "json_schema_ref", "from_edf_id", "to_edf_id" ]
}

```

This relationship is then used to express that a cluster, given by its unique ID, “runs a Pod also given by its unique ID.

2.4.2.3.3 Event Data Envelope

Events consist of an event envelope and a payload. While the envelope structure is given by MDM, the payload types are application specific. Payloads are either entities or relationships with minimal restrictions on their structure, i.e., they need to contain a type and unique identifier(s).

2.4.2.4 Interfaces

As has been explained in section 2.4.2.1, MDM can be seen as the “gateway” in CODECO towards the data world. It provides access to different metadata categories, creating K8s infrastructure knowledge graphs that can integrate data-network-compute awareness. At the current stage of architectural development, MDM is expected to interact with two additional CODECO components, ACM and PDLC. For MDM, the possibility to further understand relevant metadata also derives from the CODECO use-cases. Hence, the interfaces will also be designed taking into consideration data requirements from the use-cases (WP5).

Table 2: MDM interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-ACM-MDM-1	Metadata derived from the CODECO CRDs (other components)	OAS REST	Input
I-ACM-MDM-2	Integration of additional data types into CRDs/CRs	To be defined	Output
I-ACM-PDLC-1	Knowledge graph shared to PDLC	OAS REST	Bi-directional

2.4.2.5 Generic Operation for One Cluster

MDM interfaces to ACM to collect K8s infrastructure data (I-ACM-MDM-1), and with other data sources (I-MDM-E-1). It then stores and processes the collected metadata via the MDM API, to provide complete data observability in the cluster.

The MDM knowledge graph links all the collected information to create additional value since attributes like data lineage are shown explicitly and attributes like data classification can be derived. For example, Personal Information coming from a video feed that is processed in the cloud and stored in an S3 bucket makes in turn the contents of the S3 bucket Personal Information.

The MDM connectors are open (OAS) and are expected to be defined based on examples derived from the CODECO use-cases (WP5). New connectors can be developed as more information sources are identified both during and following the end of the project.

As illustrated in Figure 11, in each cluster MDM connectors interface to local components, including data sources (e.g., databases, file systems, IoT gateways, cloud object stores), Kubernetes (including custom resources) and other CODECO components such as NetMA, and collect relevant information. If the data source has an event interface it will trigger the information update and otherwise the collector will poll the source and generate an event to MDM. The new or updated information is added to MDM's knowledge graph, and if events have been subscribed to, an event will be generated to the relevant component. Specific elements in the generated knowledge graph with all associated metadata may be made available through CRDs to other CODECO components once those elements are identified for specific use-cases.

Figure 11: MDM single cluster operation.

The data requirements of the application workload can be exposed as part of its definition (CODECO Application model, rf. to ACM and SWM). The CODECO PDLC component integrates the information provided by MDM with the other information it collects regarding the state of applications and systems to create and evaluate models to predict their future performance. PDLC can use the MDM knowledge graph to determine how the data-related constraints may impact the execution of a workload to reduce energy consumption and support a green-IT strategy. Fewer resources will be consumed if the workload runs close to a copy of the data, for example. The scheduling in SWM can also leverage this information (derived from PDLC) in making scheduling decisions: if data is classified as being sensitive personal information, the workload processing that data should be scheduled in the same cluster or at least the same geography, depending on the policies that apply.

2.4.2.6 Considerations for Federated Clusters

Figure 12 depicts how it is initially expected that MDM is distributed over a federated clusters' environment handled with CODECO, assuming the ACM would consider a centralized control plane deployment. MDM and its API would be co-located to the ACM control plane (ACM Manager cluster), although other locations are also feasible, assuming the ACM manager cluster is a well-known entry point that can be discovered easily.

Figure 12: MDM, initial operation aspects in federated clusters.

The same way that ACM runs “clusterlets” on the managed clusters on dedicated namespaces, MDM runs connectors on dedicated namespaces (which could be the same namespace as for ACM in the context of CODECO) on those managed clusters. The goal of those connectors is to report on the information (metadata) available from the data sources and systems running on those clusters, including the clusters themselves if necessary. Each connector is specialized on a given data source or system. Connectors use the MDM Producer API to send information to the MDM graph database. Connectors may use the Kubernetes API on the cluster where they run for systems that define (through custom resource definitions or CRDs) and offer metadata through custom resources. For the systems where that is not the case, connectors may access native APIs (JDBC, for example) to obtain metadata from those systems.

The multi-cluster scenario offers the more interesting use-cases for the MDM component. Having multiple K8s clusters makes the processing of the workloads a much more complex problem, as data protection and digital management right constraints must be considered to properly schedule a workload.

As an example, a workload can specify as input data from a video surveillance system, processing the video, and storing results on some other Edge or Cloud service for archival. MDM has collected metadata on the location and nature of the data, as well as the location of the CODECO managed K8s clusters where the workload may run.

If the data source labels those videos as containing personal information, and a policy exists such that personal information can only be processed and stored in the same country from which the information originates, then this data can be used (via PDLC) to provide SWM with suitable nodes where the application workload can be run.

A similar scenario can be envisioned where the constraint is for the location of caches for a video distribution system. Digital right management constraints apply to where a video stream can be cached. For example, a movie may be cached on certain countries or regions but not on others where users are not supposed to access that content.

The constraints can be embedded into the MDM generated knowledge graph to make the querying from other components more efficient and simpler.

The MDM generated knowledge graph contains too much information to be exposed in full as a CRD. For specific use-cases, when certain nodes in the graph and their associated metadata are deemed of interest to other CODECO components, CRDs exposing information about those nodes can be created on the K8s API. For example, if datastores and their associated locations, data classification and regulations they fall under are required for a specific use-case, a CODECO MDM datastore CRD can be created with those characteristics maintained from the updated information in the MDM generated knowledge graph.

2.4.3 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration

2.4.3.1 Description

The CODECO SWM component handles the initial deployment, monitoring, and potential migration of application workloads within a single cluster and across multi-cluster environments. This implies assisting the efficient (low latency, lower energy consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) placement of applications and their containers across Edge-Cloud, derived from the information provided by PDLC (e.g., device and node availability; container centrality; network characteristics). The SWM handles, for instance, the “best” placement (based on context-awareness indicators) for the containerized components of an application to be deployed in a cluster, dealing with dynamic properties of available infrastructure, including physical/virtual machines as well as network nodes and links. Further, this placement shall be dynamically adaptable, which implies achieving the efficient (low latency, lower energy consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) migration of containerized micro-services of an application, including their state, across Edge and Cloud, derived from the information provided by PDLC (device and node availability; container centrality, network aspects).

SWM provides the following main functionality:

- **Initial placement of workloads based on the application/user QoS requirements.** SWM performs a decision for each application deployment on which workload (Pod, Container) should run on which node in a cluster, while fulfilling the QoS requirements of the application. The requirements are expressed by the user DEV via ACM, using the CODECO Application Model, and available to all CODECO components.
- **Dynamic placement of application workloads (re-scheduling).** SWM makes a new decision on placement of workloads whenever conditions change (e.g., new applications/components added, applications/components removed or changed, infrastructure conditions changed, change of QoS requirements by the user).
- **Application workload deployment and re-deployment.** SWM takes care that the workloads are executed on the selected nodes and takes remedial actions in case of failure, using native K8s mechanisms.
- **Application workload migration.** SWM manages moving a workload already running on a compute node to another compute node. This will be implemented in different qualities and steps:
 - Migration of stateless workloads.
 - Migration of stateful workloads (with service disruption).
 - Zero downtime migration of stateful workloads: without (or only small, defined) service disruption.

The high-level view of the SWM component and its interfaces is shown in Figure 13. Note that this shows the current architecture for single cluster operation.

Figure 13: SWM high-level representation.

A very basic concept that is underlying the SWM is the so-called QoS model. It is a formal model to describe on the one hand the application requirements provided by the user during setup (derived from the CODECO Application Model), and on the other hand the characteristics observed on the infrastructure (*Infrastructure Model*).

SWM resides on the control plane of K8s. It extends the K8s resource model by some CRs, making use of the K8s controller pattern to implement controllers for those resources. At the current stage of CODECO development, SWM integrates already a few CRs derived from background work, as shown in Figure 14:

- **ApplicationGroup:** Bundles a set of *Applications* that shall be placed/scheduled together. Using this construct, users can explicitly control the granularity and sequence of placement decisions.
- **Application:** Bundles a set of *Workloads* and *Channels* that belong to a (modular and distributed) application.
- **Workload:** Represents a component of an *Application*, is defined by a Workload spec that is an extension of the K8s Pod spec. Typical characteristics of a *Workload* are compute, memory, and storage requirements. In CODECO, the Workload spec is expected to be extended with new attributes, for which examples are provided in Annex I. A *Workload* maps to one or several Pods, that are deployed at a later stage.
- **Channel (object):** Represents an explicit, unidirectional communication relation of a *Workload* to other *Workloads*. Current attributes of a *Channel* are bandwidth and latency (in the sense of requirements of the application). These attributes are used by the Workload Placement Solver to match with the available network infrastructure capabilities and conditions when deciding on the placement of the *Workloads*. In CODECO, the Channel CR is expected to integrate additional attributes to further strengthen the network awareness, and to integrate a broader notion of context-awareness, as being defined in CODECO.
- **Channel (CR):** Each *Channel* object will be mapped to a *Channel* CR that represents an explicit communication service in the network infrastructure. Depending on the underlying network technology and service class, it may be possible or required to setup communication services to reserve network resources and to guarantee certain QoS requirements for *Channels* between *Workloads* that are placed on different nodes. The

Channel resource keeps track and manages the lifecycle and states of such a communication service, handling the required interactions with the respective service endpoints of the network infrastructure. As the QoS guarantees in CODECO are provided via NetMA with a new level of sophistication, this CR may or may not be handled via NetMA.

- **Endpoint:** Represents worker nodes in the cluster. It covers aspects of the nodes that are not covered by the K8s standard resource *Node*. Currently, it is used to keep information about network interfaces and related addresses (IP and MAC) on the nodes. Additional aspects and information related to the worker nodes may be added to the *Endpoint* CR, like ,e.g., information on its specific energy consumption, availability (current and projected). It is envisioned that the *Endpoint* CR may be controlled by another CODECO component (e.g., ACM). Examples of new attributes that may be considered are provided in Annex I.
- **NetworkLink:** Represents the links of the underlying communication network that interconnects the compute nodes of the cluster. Current attributes of a *NetworkLink* are bandwidth, available bandwidth, and latency. Network awareness shall be further extended in CODECO, being currently envisioned that the *NetworkLink* CR will be controlled by another CODECO component, NetMA. A first sub-set of attributes is provided in Annex I. A *NetworkLink* connects an *Endpoint* or *NetworkNode* with another *Endpoint* or *NetworkNode*.
- **NetworkNode:** Object that represents internal nodes of the communication network infrastructure like switches or routers. Currently, *NetworkNodes* are passive, and they do not carry attributes. They are currently used to express/construct the network topology that is part of the QoS Model. In the context of CODECO, it is envisioned that *NetworkNodes* will be CRs controlled by NetMa.
- **NetworkPath:** Besides the physical network topology, the paths (or routes) that can be used to transmit data between any pair of endpoints are relevant to decide on usage and/or allocation of network resources. In the current implementation, *NetworkPaths* are calculated by SWM from the existing network topology, as SWM has already addressed a specific use-case based on *Time Sensitive Networking (TSN)*. In CODECO, NetMA handles the overall routing integration with K8s based on SDN. Hence, the *NetworkPath* CR is also expected to be handled via NetMA.
- **AssignmentPlan:** CR that contains the result of the placement decision, as returned by the Workload Placement Solver. This includes for an *ApplicationGroup*: for all *Workloads* the *Nodes* they shall be placed on, and for all *Channels* the *NetworkPath* that shall be used.

2.4.3.2 Key technologies

The initial design and components of SWM is based on the SIE existing background implementation of “Seamless Computing” [5]. The “Seamless Computing Orchestrator” is built as an extension to the K8s control plane, making use of new CRDs/CRs and respective controllers and operators. Main technologies in SWM are:

- K8s, the K8s control plane and the K8s extended API; the controller and scheduling frameworks.
- Google Remote Procedure Call (gRPC) and Protocol Buffers (Protobuf).
- Go programming language (Golang).

Figure 14: Current SWM CRs and objects.

2.4.3.3 Sub-components

As illustrated in Figure 14, SWM is composed of the following components:

- **Extended K8s API/ CODECO CRs.** The main API of SWM is the (extended) K8s API. It serves as an API to users of SWM (e.g., to deploy applications, or to request status information about them), but also as a system interface towards the compute infrastructure via the Kubelets running on the worker nodes (e.g., to update resource information about the compute nodes, or to instruct the deployment of Pods on a worker node). It is also via this API that SWM interacts with other CODECO components, as illustrated in Figure 13. The interfaces to other CODECO components are expected to be implemented as SWM CRs, either as an extension of the existing SWM CRs, or as new ones. The specific content of these CRs still needs to be fine-tuned according to the specific requirements of the CODECO use-cases.
- **QoS model.** The QoS Model is used by SWM to decide on the placement of workloads of an application. It is not a component, but a data model that is used in different places, as has been explained in section 2.4.3.1. Information on the current QoS model adopted in SWM, and additional changes required due to the interaction with other components is provided in section 2.4.3.3.1 (SWM QoS Model).
- **SWM controller-manager.** The SWM controller-manager bundles a couple of SWM custom controllers that manage SWM CRs, which have been described in section 2.4.3.1 (SWM Description).
- **QoS Scheduler.** The QoS Scheduler is a custom scheduler that is built using the K8s scheduling framework²², it runs as a Pod in the K8s cluster, and it registers as scheduler to the K8s control plane. It implements the so-called scheduling plugins for certain phases of the K8s scheduling lifecycle. While the K8s standard scheduler schedules each Pod individually, one of the specific mechanisms of the QoS Scheduler is that it decides on the placement of all Pods of an *ApplicationGroup* at once. This is required to consider dependencies between the Pods (e.g., communication relations and QoS), and to treat the Pod placement as a graph problem, rather than a sequential, linear problem. The

22 <https://github.com/kubernetes/enhancements/tree/master/keps/sig-scheduling/624-scheduling-framework>

deployment of the Pods within an *ApplicationGroup* is held back, until the placement decision is taken, and all communication resources have been confirmed (if applicable).

- **Workload Placement Solver.** The Workload Placement Solver is called by the SWM controller-manager to determine the placement of the workloads of all Applications in an *ApplicationGroup*. There can be different implementations of Workload Placement Solvers. The API uses gRPC, where the QoS Model (call of Workload Placement Solver) and the placement decision (returned result) are described as Protobuf. The Workload Placement Solver is deployed as a Pod in K8s. In CODECO, an implementation of a simple solver will be provided as source code and could also be used as blueprint to implement further solvers, optimizers, or heuristics (e.g., learning-based implementations). A more sophisticated optimizer will be made available as container image for use within the CODECO project.

2.4.3.3.1 QoS Model

The SWM QoS model consists of two parts: the *Application Model* and the *Infrastructure Model*.

The *Application Model* describes distributed, modular applications, that consist of workloads that communicate via interfaces. The attributes of an application are expressing the QoS requirements of the application. The *Infrastructure Model* currently describes the hardware entities that form the execution environment for the applications. It consists of compute and network infrastructure, particularly compute nodes, network nodes, and network links. The attributes of the Infrastructure Model express the resources and capabilities of the infrastructure.

Further data may be required to define the decision objective, i.e., the criteria that are optimized or at least used as guidance to prioritize and finally select a placement of the workloads of an application. It is intended to make the objective adaptable by providing a generic objective with adjustable weights. Moreover, as CODECO counts also with additional data enrichment derived from MDM and from PDLC (sub-component CA; and, from the learning components), the QoS model(s) in SWM are expected to have to be adjusted to this new context. Hence, CODECO is expected to provide the basis for a richer definition of QoS levels to be supported. Moreover, from a network perspective (NetMA), the QoS levels should take into consideration the IP perspective following a model such as Differentiated Services (DiffServ).

The current implementation of the SIE background *Seamless Computing* concept supports QoS based on 2 levels (Assured and Best Effort). As NetMA brings a new level of network awareness, the specific QoS guarantees to be provided will be discussed with NetMA. In case of changes, SWM will have to be adapted. It should be noticed that for usage in CODECO, the Seamless Computing implementation is currently redesigned in a way that each communication service level maps to an appropriate network infrastructure technology, and each network infrastructure technology will require a network controller. Hence, assuming CODECO adopts (as an example) another QoS model, such as DiffServ, then, the respective CRs and operators will have to be handled in NetMa.

2.4.3.3.2 QoS Scheduler Extension Mechanisms

It is intended to provide extension mechanisms to alter the behaviour of the SWM QoS scheduler without having to change the implementation. Now, three mechanisms are envisioned:

- Based on (generic) labels (used in the SWM Application YAML and set on Endpoint CRs).
- Based on weights/costs of the Endpoints and/or NetworkLinks (set on CRs).

- Based on objective weights for the WorkloadPlacementSolver (set in the SWM Application YAML, using classes with pre-configured weights, like e.g., “Energy-focus”, “Cost-focus”). These weights may also be passed from PDLC to SWM.

2.4.3.4 Interfaces

The current interfaces of SWM to other components, identified in Figure 13, are summarized in Table 3. The current assumption is that the interfaces between SWM and other components are realized via K8s CRs. One advantage of this is, that the K8s API already provides extensive means of access rights and control.

Table 3: SWM interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-SWM-ACM-1	Access/integration with CRs/operators handled by SWM and other CODECO components, e.g., NetMA	CR	Bi-directional
I-SWM-ACM-2	Registration, configuration, and operation of QoS Scheduler	K8s scheduling framework	Bi-directional
I-PDLC-SWM-1,2	PDLC will set attributes of custom resources of the infrastructure model, that are used by SWM to influence the placement decision for workloads. This can relate to combined costs (I-PDLC-SWM-1) or to behaviour estimation (I-PDLC-SWM-2). Currently, the relevant custom resources are <i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i> . PDLC can also make use of the QoS Scheduler extensions.	CR	Input
I-SWM-PDLC-1	PDLC will be able to know about scheduling/placement decisions of SWM by accessing the <i>AssignmentPlan</i> CR	CR	Output
I-SWM-NET-1	Used to request NetMA to perform QoS reservations. SWM may perform requests for reservations to NetMA, based on the scheduling/placement decisions. Furthermore, NetMA may also handle network-related CRs (<i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i>) to reflect network conditions.	CR	Bi-directional

As has also been explained, SWM may perform QoS reservation requests to NetMA. Assuming interface I-SWM-NET-1 would be based on the CR *Channel*, then NetMA would have to implement a controller²³ that handles the reservations.

As next steps, we expect that NetMA handles QoS reservations per type of network QoS model adopted (e.g., DiffServ, L2VPN), thus requiring a CR/controller per network QoS model. Such controller would also be responsible to observe and manage the respective CR and react by implementing all steps to establish an end-to-end connection with the required QoS settings and to indicate success or failure via appropriate states.

²³ A simple network controller for best effort networks is being implemented as blueprint as part of the current redesign of Seamless Computing.

2.4.3.5 Generic Operation for one Cluster

A so-called QoS deployment works as follows:

- Via ACM, the user describes the application QoS requirements via the CODECO Application Model (one or more YAML files). SWM relies on this file to create the description of the desired deployment, considering the CRs ApplicationGroup and Application (including Workloads, Channels, and all relevant attributes).
- Once the minimum number of Applications that are part of the ApplicationGroup is created, the ApplicationGroup custom controller collects all information required for the placement (QoS Model).
- Both the SWM Application and Infrastructure Models are compiled based on the CODECO Application Model, obtained via ACM.
 - The Application Model considers the CRs: Applications, Workloads, Interfaces.
 - The Infrastructure Model is compiled by retrieving information from the related infrastructure custom resources: Node, Endpoint, NetworkLink, NetworkNode, NetworkPath.
- The ApplicationGroup custom controller calls the Workload Placement Solver, handing over the QoS Model.
- The Workload Placement Solver determines a placement for the workloads of the applications, considering all constraints and (if it is an optimizing solver) optimized according to the defined objective. The result is returned and placed in the CR AssignmentPlan.
- For each Workload that could be placed, a Pod is created, the preferred node for the Pod is set according to the placement decision. However, deployment of the Pods is still held back.
- For each Channel between Workloads that could be placed, a CR Channel is created. Channels between Workloads that are placed on the same node are tagged as “*loopback channels*” (they do not require connections over the network).
- For all other Channels, the respective network controller (watching the creation of the Channel) will react accordingly. Depending on the network technology and implementation of the network controller, a reaction could be keeping track of occupied bandwidth for the Channel, and/or reserving/establishing an end-to-end channel through the network. In any case, success, or failure of the establishment of an end-to-end channel needs to be reported via the state of the CR Channel.
- Once all Channels of the ApplicationGroup are in state “ACKNOWLEDGED”, the deployment of the Pods of the ApplicationGroup will be kicked off.
- K8s will deploy the Pods, resulting in downloading and starting the appropriate containers in the selected nodes, and the Applications will become operational.

2.4.3.6 Considerations for Federated Clusters

No considerations at the current stage of the project.

2.4.4 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness

2.4.4.1 Description

PDLC integrates, as the name points out, 3 sub-modules: privacy preservation; decentralised learning; context-awareness, illustrated in Figure 15. The PDLC-CA is a sub-component that, based on metrics collected via other CODECO components, and/or available via K8s plugins, correlates different categories of metrics such as application requirements (ACM); user behaviour and feedback (ACM); data aspects (MDM); node (ACM) and network functional and

non-functional requirements (NetMA). Its output, which concerns a set of computed weights related with the desired performance optimization (e.g., greenness level of the multi-cluster environment; QoS needs; privacy needs and privacy-preserving adaptations, sovereignty needs; soft network characteristics, e.g., network lifetime stability), is fed to the PDLC-DL sub-module and expected to be directly provided to other modules, currently to SWM and to ACM. CODECO shall explore novel, decentralised learning approaches (e.g., Swarm learning), to assist a cross-layer adaptation of data-computation-network.

Hence, PDLC corresponds to the component that handles context acquisition and modelling, and a ML-based orchestration engine, which can assist SWM in making an informed scheduling/re-scheduling decision, based on behaviour prediction. This is developed via two micro-services as illustrated in Figure 9. Specifically, there are two main subcomponents of PDLC:

- **Context-Awareness (PDLC-CA):** the subcomponent responsible for data gathering, integration and pre-processing (PDLC-DP) to generate exploitable context information and performance profiling (PDLC-PP).
- **Decentralised Learning (PDLC-DL):** the subcomponent responsible for exploiting the context information provided by PDLC-CA through privacy-aware decentralised learning algorithm to add an additional intelligence layer to the operations of CODECO.

Figure 15 depicts the interactions of the different PDLC sub-components with other CODECO components, namely ACM, MDM, and SWM. The interfaces needed for these interactions are explained in Section 2.4.4.4.

Figure 15: PDLC high-level architecture and interfaces.

The role of each component is as follows:

- **ACM.** PDLC relies, similarly to other CODECO components, on the CRDs/CRs managed by other components. ACM will also potentially receive output from PDLC-PP in the form of recommendations about initial cluster configurations, once enough historical data has been gathered and learning models have been trained.
- **MDM:** May provide, in addition to the MDM CRs. additional data information to PDLC, related to data-related issues that may impact orchestration decisions. For instance, if an application requires access to large data sets, depending on network bandwidth and latency constraints, it may be necessary to constrain where the data is processed to achieve performance requirements. Similarly, data compliance constraints may restrict where sensitive data can be copied and therefore constrain where it is processed. MDM provides a complete set of metadata describing the data (e.g., location, size,

classification, policy evaluation) to assist CODECO in making orchestration decisions that are cognizant of data constraints.

- **SWM**: the main component to receive output from PDLC, both in the form of performance profiling as well as behaviour estimation and optimization. Crucially, SWM might need to provide feedback to PDLC about the decisions it makes based on the provided output, which would allow PDLC-PP and PDLC-DL to compare their suggestions with the taken actions and use that feedback to improve.

2.4.4.2 Key Technologies

- Federator.ai²⁴ and alameda.ai²⁵ as basis for the optimal matching derived from application deployment constraints (CODECO Application model) and application workload needs.
- Prometheus, and new Prometheus CODECO operators, to observe and provide metrics to PDLC.
- Pytorch²⁶, Pytorch Lightning²⁷ for the comparative ML models analysis, and PDLC-DL implementation.
- TensorFlow Lite²⁸ and other TinyML frameworks, for integration of selected models in embedded devices.

2.4.4.3 Sub-components

2.4.4.3.1 Context-aware PDLC Component (PDLC-CA)

The PDLC-CA sub-component holds different micro-services as illustrated in Figure 15. The PDLC-CA obtains metrics (e.g., compute metrics, network metrics) via ACM (I-PDLC-ACM-1; CRD/CRs controlled by other CODECO components; Prometheus operator(s)) (rf. to the next sub-section, 2.4.4.3.2) and may also obtain additional metadata via MDM (I-PDLC-MDM-1). Specific parameters and categories of metrics to be considered are described in the next sub-section (2.4.4.3.2). The metrics are then worked (aggregated) to provide a finer-grain performance target. For instance, assuming the user considers as main priority to optimize the available infrastructure in terms of energy, PDLC-CA will rely on specific heuristics to provide a cost per infrastructure element (nodes, network nodes, network links, eventually network paths) that takes into consideration not just compute resources but also data and network resources.

The output of PDLC-CA is internally provided to the PDLC-DL component, core of the ML-based orchestration in CODECO, to ACM (I-PDLC-ACM-2) and to SWM (I-PDLC-SWM-1). The next sub-sections explain the PDLC-CA micro-services; interfaces are further discussed in section 2.4.4.4.

2.4.4.3.2 Input Data, Collection, and Storage Aspects

In current container orchestration solutions, the need to replicate resources is usually based on system requirements (e.g., CPU usage of a node reaches a specific level, or energy level is perceived as high); application requirements (e.g., bounded latency); network policies. To further support dynamic Edge-Cloud environments, container orchestration needs to integrate context-awareness into the offloading process. *Context-awareness* refers to the capability of a system to consider knowledge about its environment, to perform specific actions. In this

24 <https://catalog.redhat.com/software/container-stacks/detail/5e9872c4d4ae96b7493f08e0>

25 <https://github.com/containers-ai/alameda>

26 <https://pytorch.org/>

27 <https://lightning.ai/docs/pytorch/latest/>

28 <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

context, a system can be a computational system; a cyber-physical system; a set of cyber-physical systems [5][7]. Usually, contextual information falls into a wide range of categories such as computing context (e.g., available processors, memory, nearby resources); user context (e.g., location, user profiles, nearby users); environmental context (e.g., lighting, temperature).

A first step towards achieving context-aware orchestration is the definition of a basic set of context-awareness parameter categories to consider in the offloading process, how to model context, and how such modelling can be integrated.

In CODECO, the initial proposal derives from prior analysis by partner FOR [8] is to consider the following categories of context-aware metrics as illustrated in Figure 16, and specific examples of attributes are provided in Annex I:

- **System metrics** refer to internal parameters of a system and are usually available already to K8s. Examples are CPU, memory, as in K8s.
- **Network metrics** relate to both functional QoS requirements (e.g., RTT, latency, allocated bandwidth between worker nodes and the master node); and to non-functional QoS/QoE requirements (e.g., mobility, portability).
- **Application metrics** relate with application QoS parameters. For instance, In the context of Industrial IoT critical applications often require minimum and bounded latency within one msec. Tight time synchronization among devices serving a specific application is often a challenge, due to time-aware queuing disciplines that support the exchange of critical traffic. Non-functional requirements, such as a sensitiveness level of an application, or even certification or compliance aspects, may prevent an application to run under specific conditions on a node.
- **Data observability metrics** relate with dataset characteristics, e.g., freshness of the data, compliance verification towards a specific location.
- **User behaviour metrics** relate with the user behaviour as a carrier/controller of applications in the far Edge. A common indicator of user behaviour is user location, which is widely applied. Other forms of user behaviour, including user preferences, have been considered, e.g., social interaction, group formation, and social/physical proximity to improve overall system performance and to provide better support for task offloading across the Edge [9][10].

Figure 16: Examples of context-aware parameters in CODECO.

As has been explained regarding ACM (rf. to section 2.4.1) and to the MDM component (rf. to section 2.4.2), several CODECO components shall collect metrics. The collection and monitoring of such metrics is to be handled via the integration of new Prometheus operators in CODECO (via ACM). PDLC-CA does not therefore collect data; instead, it shall regularly obtain metrics from available CRs, and eventually from Prometheus. The data input interfaces

(I-PDLC-ACM-1 and I-MDM-PDLC-1) are (M6) still under discussion (WP3). Examples for how the data can be collected by the different components is as follows:

- **Application and user behaviour/preferences - ACM.** This data is obtained during setup of an application deployment via the CODECO Application Model, which is being designed to capture functional and non-functional requirements from user DEV. The definition of this (or multiple) application-level model is a task of the CA in PDLC; initial metrics being considered are provided in Annex I. The ACM would handle the transformation into a K8s declarative object configuration file.
- **Data observability – MDM.** MDM can tag events that relate with data observability, e.g., if a dataset is not updated within a specified time, or if a dataset grows to exceed a specified size, a trigger to be generated to schedule application to handle the condition.
- **Network parameters – NetMA.** Via ALTO, NetMA is expected to collect relevant network parameters that assist in a better definition of the infrastructure, beyond the usual view of resources provided in K8s. The starting parameters are in Annex I. Additional categories of network data may rely among others, with security aspects, resilience aspects.

PDLC shall rely on CRDs/CRs provided by other components; and transform the existing metrics into an aggregated perspective, that can provide costs per infrastructure element based on a combination of compute, data, network, and user preferences. Hence, the infrastructure is treated as a graph problem, as required by the CODECO SWM component, but the purpose is to generate an aggregated perspective of a node betweenness value based on data, compute, network resources.

At the current stage of development, the proposed output may not be sufficient to achieve an appropriate placement as being devised in SWM. Therefore, next steps of development shall consider the requirements from SWM, where the placement decision requires a distinction between hard constraints (constraints that must be filled to achieve a valid placement solution, and which are provided by the CODECO Application Model YAML file(s)) and soft objectives (performance profiling targets in accordance with selected criteria). Aggregated costs can be considered on the latter.

2.4.4.3.2.1 Data Availability Considerations

The PDLC component, in particular the learning part, heavily relies on data collected. Such data (metrics) will be in practice provided via the CODECO use-cases (WP5). To allow the development of PDLC to advance, CODECO considers a standalone synthetic data generator that shall mimic the CODECO data workflow. The generator simulates the process of the cross-layer data collection, and as output results in a consistent data format for further analysis by the PDLC sub-components.

2.4.4.3.3 Data Pre-processing (PDLC-PD)

Within PDLC-CA, the collected data will be pre-processed before it can be exploited by PDLC-PP and PDLC-DL subcomponents. The exact steps will be further defined once the definition of the initial data is finalized.

One aspect that can be considered is data aggregation / clustering, which is a fundamental unsupervised learning technique that groups unlabelled data points based on their similarity. This approach can be particularly useful for context awareness, where the objective is to extract meaningful information from diverse cross-layer data sources, resulting in more meaningful contextual information. Clustering models like hierarchical, density-based, and spectral can be applied to extract meaningful labels, annotate the pre-processed data, and provide more contextualized data.

Figure 17: A sample data pre-processing pipeline used as a baseline for PDLC-DP.

Also, additional analysis tools such as *Dynamic time wrapping*, and *time-varying causal inference* can be used as supportive methods to reflect the context-awareness part. Dynamic Time Wrapping measures the similarity between two temporal time sequences that have different lengths and can provide additional insights that facilitate context-awareness. Time-varying causal inference is a method used to analyse the relationships between variables that change over time and to identify cause-and-effect relationships between the cross-layer data and the system's current context (e.g., effects of environmental factors on the nodes health).

2.4.4.3.4 Context-aware Performance Profiling (PDLC-PP)

The pre-processed datasets are then made available to the context-aware performance profiling block of the sub-component PDLC-CA, named as PDLC-PP.

This micro-service performs a combination of the received data sets based of pre-configured heuristics that aim at providing a measure of performance, for a specific performance efficiency profile. For instance, assuming a user wants to optimize the system for greenness, then this block would select and combine weighted context datasets (e.g., hop count, energy consumption) in accordance with a specific function (e.g., product of hop count and energy consumption).

Hence, this micro-service is being developed to provide support to other plugins in K8s (towards kube-scheduler, I-PDLC-ACM-2) and to provide an aggregated result to SWM (I-PDLC-SWM-1).

At the current stage, the output to other components is expected to be provided either/or in the form of a knowledge graph, or a specific CR to be developed for that purpose. **This second option is the preferred one as it fits better the current design of SWM.** PDLC does not handle any decision in terms of placement (scheduling, re-scheduling).

The combination of parameters shall be weighted, i.e., the different categories of context parameters are weighted according to data preferences, or even according to learning over time, provided via feedback provided by the DL-based offloading decision engine.

2.4.4.3.5 Decentralised Learning sub-component (PDLC-DL)

PDLC-DL is responsible for all learning aspects in the CODECO framework. It received input from the context-awareness sub-component and can provide output to all other components that need it. Currently, the generated output is expected to be made available via a PDLC CR to other components. For the case of SWM, the infrastructure-related CRs (Endpoint, NetworkNode, NetworkLink, NetworkPath) may be considered. In addition, it may also be considered that PDLC may alter or complement certain parameters of the application-oriented CRs (requirements/attributes contained in the application deployment request – YAML – of the user DEV). The output of PDLC can be seen as a set of altered or additional parameters that could be provided to the SWM CRs, and that enable more informed placement decisions.

2.4.4.3.5.1 Input and Output

The input data that PDLC-DL will train the models on will be gathered, transformed, and curated by PDLC-CA. Thus, DL is not expected to have direct communications with other components of CODECO to retrieve any input data. On the other hand, the output that DL generates, whether it is an optimization, estimation, or prediction, shall be consumed directly by the component(s) that requires such output – at the current stage, as has been described, this refers to SWM only.

Another component that may benefit from the output of PDLC-DL is ACM (towards Prometheus): the output would relate in this case with feedback on the infrastructure improvements, due to the PDLC-DL recommendations provided to SWM.

2.4.4.3.5.2 Continuous vs. On-demand Learning

An aspect that is under development is whether PDLC-DL will consider a continuous learning approach, or an on-demand learning approach.

Assuming CODECO adopts a continuous learning approach, then models are continuously generating output that is forwarded to the corresponding components. This alternative requires a continuous flow of the cross-layer input data from PDLC-CA, which implies more frequent updates, and a need for a more robust data collection process, which may bring problems for federated clusters environments (data collection from different CODECO components, via CRs; data collection via MDM across distributed databases). This can cause complications in the data collection processes, especially if dealing with local scoped data (e.g., private, or protected data due to local regulation). Moreover, with a continuous learning approach, the output generated by PDLC-DL will also be continuous. For the case of SWM, this may not be feasible as it may create frequent proposals for changes in placement. Finally, continuous learning usually provides a higher degree of precision, but it may be harder to implement and maintain.

As for an on-demand approach, then the PDLC output would only be produced when requested by other components, which is more aligned to the way that SWM currently performs the placement decisions. In other words, the PDLC-DL model(s) will be trained and deployed but will not receive continuous input data. In this alternative, the output interfaces will be a type of API (REST for example) with one or more endpoints to be invoked by other CODECO components.

At the current stage of CODECO development, PDLC-DL adopts an on-demand learning approach.

2.4.4.3.5.3 Types of Models

The type of model(s) to be trained will depend on the input data available and the objectives required from PDLC. This aspect is therefore highly related with the CODECO use-cases, and expected data – at the current deployment stage, the CODECO use-cases have already provided an initial design of the data expected to be generated (rf. to Deliverable D8); however, the expected dataset features will still have to be obtained or generated.

Moreover, the development of PDLC-DL (WP3) needs also to decide whether one or more models will be used. For instance, we can envision one optimization model that provides output for several CODECO components, or several models that provide multiple outputs.

Some candidates of algorithms and models that might be suitable for PDLC-DL are:

- **Reinforcement Learning (RL)** [12][13][14]. RL is based on the notion that an agent must learn to adjust its behaviour within the dynamic environment that it interacts with by exploring and exploiting the search space and therefore to provide the best action/recommendation based on the specific environment's situation. Alternatives within RL include on-policy methods, which attempt to evaluate or improve the same policy that is used to make decisions, or off-policy methods, which explore the environment and attempt to learn the optimal policy based on the system's behaviour. RL can also be implemented in a decentralised manner, by adopting *Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL)* [15], which is suitable for the federated vision of PDLC-DL and the CODECO framework. In MARL, multiple agents across CODECO edge nodes can be trained with their own contextual data to provide the respective actions that maximize their cumulative reward.
- **Encoder-Decoder Architectures (EDAs)** [16][17][18]: EDAs are a form of *Neural Networks (NN)* that learn a representation of data that captures its contextual information. EDAs are designed to handle sequence-to-sequence problems where the input and output sequences can have variable lengths and complex relationships. This is a suitable approach that can fit CODECO since the data that are handled are mostly in the form of time series. Specifically, contextual data derived from PDLC-CA can be fed into an encoder model to produce an encoder vector and on the other side the decoder will produce the desired output. Proposed algorithms that can serve PDLC-DL include a) *Long-Term Short Memory (LSTM)*; *Gate Recurrent Unit (GRU)* NN; and Convolutional-based EDAs, b) Attention-based EDAs that are more effective at capturing complex relationships in time series data, or c) Transformer-based EDAs that rely on self-attention mechanisms and do not use recurrent connections like LSTMs or GRUs.
- **Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)** [19][20][21]. This class of NN is beneficial in processing and learning from data that can be represented as graphs. GNNs are used *in lieu* of conventional ML/DL models, which are specialized in simpler and more uniform data types. In the case of CODECO, the Cloud, near Edge and far Edge nodes can be represented as graphs. GNNs can then be used to optimize attributes of the graph representation of the infrastructure. For instance, weights can be assigned to the different edges of the graph, which represent the connections between the continuum nodes, and the GNN can optimize the data transfers, load-balancing, or application deployment based on these weights.

2.4.4.3.5.4 Automation, Maintenance, and Deployment

To deploy ML models that will efficiently receive data from other components and output a multi-objective estimation, well-designed MLOps techniques will be employed within CODECO framework. As in most ML pipelines, the first steps should include the data gathering and the pre-processing of the input features, and the training of decentralised models. Once the decentralised learning process is complete, the CODECO MLOps process will proceed with deploying the trained models to their target environment/ proper edge nodes. This involves packaging the models, integrating them into the target system, and monitoring their performance and behaviour. Model monitoring will help in detecting anomalies, ensuring model fairness and accuracy, and triggering retraining or updating of models, when necessary, which leads to a completely self-training and self-healing cloud-edge-far edge continuum.

2.4.4.4 Interfaces

The current interfaces of PDLC to other components, identified in Figure 15 , are summarized in Table 4. **The full interaction from MDM to PDLC and from PDLC to SWM requires still additional analysis. In what concerns MDM-PDLC, the following options are being explored:**

- MDM can provide a “snapshot” of the infrastructure derived from the data perspective, based on the data constrains, based on an MDM CR. This would require the MDM API to convert the current output format (knowledge graph) into a CR, and to handle also the respective controller managing the CR, OR
- PDLC can obtain the MDM API output (graphDB format, for instance), and perform a transformation to a CR format that can then be accessed by other components.

About the PDLC-SWM interfacing, what is being proposed is that PDLC accesses the SWM CR AssignmentPlan. The constrains concerning a specific application deployment are available via the CODECO Application Model.

Table 4: PDLC interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-PDLC-ACM-1	Obtaining data collected by other CODECO components and made available via CRs of those components.	CRs	Input
I-PDLC-ACM-2	Output of the combined infrastructure view, via a PDLC CR	CR	Output
I-MDM-PDLC-1	Data collected by CODECO MDM	Knowledge graph, e.g., graphDB	Input
I-PDLC-SWM-1,2	PDLC will set attributes of custom resources of the infrastructure model, which are used by SWM to influence the placement decision for workloads. This can relate to combined costs (I-PDLC-SWM-1) or to behaviour estimation (I-PDLC-SWM-2). Currently, the relevant custom resources are <i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i> . PDLC can also make use of the QoS Scheduler extensions.	CR	Output
I-SWM-PDLC-1	PDLC will be able to know about scheduling/placement decisions of SWM by accessing the <i>AssignmentPlan</i> CR	CR	Input
I-NET-PDLC-1	NetMA asks infrastructure element estimation from PDLC-DL	CR	Output

2.4.4.5 Generic operation for One Cluster

PDLC is currently being developed, and its sub-components are still in an early stage of development (TRL2-3). As a first iteration and to start testing PDLC in conjunction with other CODECO components as soon as possible, we suggest the single-cluster deployment scenario depicted in Figure 18, which depicts a single CODECO cluster with multiple nodes.

Figure 18: Deployment and operation of PDLC within a single CODECO cluster.

As can be observed, we propose to perform the PDLC-DL model training in the master node and to deploy the trained model on each worker node of the cluster. These deployed models can then be invoked locally, thus meaning that the data needed to invoke them can also be collected locally by PDLC-CA and does not need to be shared outside of the worker node.

To retrain and update the models, input data needs to be periodically sent from the worker nodes to the master node where the model training occurs. This process can include filtering and privacy-preserving measure for personal data before it is sent from the different worker nodes (e.g., aggregation, anonymization). The model retraining process will be done semi-automatically, meaning that it will need a manual validation step of the results before the new model is redeployed to the worker nodes.

Note that the deployment mechanisms for a multi-cluster scenario will be handled in WP4 and will need coordination with the partners responsible for the corresponding task to align the single-cluster model types and deployment with their needs and expectations.

2.4.4.6 Considerations for federated clusters

To be provided on a later stage of architectural development (M20).

2.4.5 NetMa: Network Management and Adaptation

2.4.5.1 Description

NetMA is a network management and adaptation solution that automates the setup of interconnections for flexible Edge-Cloud operations, while addressing the integration of internetworking control and supporting the needs of diverse network environments (fixed, wireless, cellular) that are expected to be managed by CODECO. This CODECO component handles aspects such as network softwarization, semantic interoperability, secure data exchange, predictive behaviour, and integrated network capability exposure through standard-based mechanisms and K8s APIs. Also, AI/ML techniques are applied to learn from network events for closed-loop automation and adaptive control.

The areas of network softwarization that NetMA works on include providing *Function-as-a-Service (FaaS)* to the Edge and automating network resource management to accommodate specialized service requirements. To promote the integration of various networking domains

and increase the physical footprint of computing facilities, it also ensures semantic compatibility between internetworking services, like the Gaia-X semantic network model. Figure 19 represents the three main NetMA goals and how this component interacts with other CODECO modules at a high-level view. The scope and complexity of the communications and data exchange will depend on the deployment and operational process, being for instance larger in scenarios requiring connectivity redundancies, multi-clustering or multidomain interconnection.

Figure 19: NetMA high-level goals and interaction with CODECO components.

NetMA prioritizes security and includes procedures for infrastructure and function certification and verification. Therefore, to accomplish a trustworthy and sovereign data exchange between Edge services, the *International Data Spaces (IDS)*²⁹ Reference Architecture model will be adopted. Moreover, NetMA leverages standard-based mechanisms like ALTO and APIs like the *ETSI Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)* to expose integrated network capabilities, and collects pertinent networking metrics which, via PDLC analysis, may be used to further forecast a more adaptive network behaviour.

Figure 20 illustrates NetMA and its sub-components, as well as initial interfaces to other CODECO components.

NetMA operates by providing an abstraction layer of the underlay network in CODECO. This component is responsible to provide connectivity services according to requirements representing *Service Level Objectives (SLOs)* as an expectation of QoS demanded for that service. For this purpose, the NetMA component is responsible to map the traffic flows to the proper connectivity constructs satisfying the required SLOs along the connectivity service lifetime. Conceptually, the connectivity service provided will follow the notion of network slice in the sense of tailoring the connectivity construct to the needs of the connectivity consumer.

In order to simplify the connectivity service provisioning and operation, the approach is to provide connectivity services in the form of overlays that can be extended across multiple network domains (including multiple provider scenarios) in a smooth manner, simplifying the overall provisioning process and making transparent for the CODECO system all the complexities and particularities of the network domains (i.e., aspects such as IP addressing, different programmatic capabilities in the underlay network, operation across domains, etc).

²⁹ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>

Along the project, mechanisms will be defined for adapting that overlay connectivity services to the specific needs as requested by the connectivity consumers. Basically, traffic engineering mechanisms are planned for providing tailored connectivity services.

Figure 20: NetMA High-level architecture.

The NetMA component will also expose information of the underlay network to other components in CODECO. The initial information considered to be exposed is about topology and monitoring data.

In this sense, NetMA plans to provide topological information regarding reachability of distinct compute domains participating in CODECO, i.e., attached edge and cloud sites, together with performance data associated to the connectivity among those sites, so that CODECO components can build a view of the expected metrics impacting the overall service. In its interaction with other CODECO modules, NetMA will provide this information to MDM and SWM to feed their models. It is also in roadmap the objective of populating the compute resources available on those sites, being this a matter of further investigation at the time of writing this deliverable.

In conclusion, the NetMA component will work as an abstraction layer of the K8s Pod overlay network (single and multi-cluster), making a transparent handling of the connectivity resources of the involved Network Domains (NDs) interconnecting edge and cloud sites forming the Compute Domain (CD). When a request for connectivity with specific SLOs for QoS guarantees is required (during a K8s deployment, i.e., during the scheduling/re-scheduling process), NetMA is the CODECO component that handles the network slicing and network management process, as well as reservations, if required. NetMA also collects network metrics (topological, resilience) and provides such information to other components via CRD/CRs, accessible via ACM/K8s.

2.4.5.2 Key Technologies

- The **ALTO**³⁰ **protocol and framework**, as the basis for building a network capability exposure mechanism.
- **L2S-M**³¹ as mechanism for providing link-layer secure connectivity for microservice platforms, for creating and managing virtual networks in K8s clusters.
- The **π -Edge Platform** from Partner ICOM, as the sub-component that handles the onboarding in the far Edge; exposure of network information to other components (via CRs).
- **EdgeX Foundry**³², as an open-source IoT Platform completely integrated with the π -Edge Platform, for facilitating interoperability between IoT devices and application at the Edge/ far Edge.
- **Eclipse Dataspace Connector**³³, for establishing a secure data exchange mechanism and ensuring data interoperability.
- **Argo Workflows**³⁴ for orchestrating FaaS network services using Kubernetes CRDs.

2.4.5.3 Sub-components

As illustrated in Figure 20, NetMA currently considers the following sub-components:

- **Network exposure, based on ALTO** [11]. The ALTO framework provides network information to applications (i.e., ALTO clients) so that they can make more informed decisions about how to optimize network traffic as generated by such applications. It can be seen, then, as a *Network Exposure Function (NEF)* of the underlying transport network. ALTO, illustrated in Figure 21, enables applications to obtain network information, such as network topology and performance metrics, from network service providers running the connectivity infrastructure. By using this information, applications can make decisions about which paths to take through the network to optimize their traffic flows for improving their performance. Apart from that, recent proposals in standardization propose to use ALTO for incorporating new data sources such as the available compute resources connected to network domains. ALTO is seen as an important tool for exposing network information for optimizing traffic in distributed applications, such as those used in Edge-Cloud environments.
- **Automation, based on the ICOM π -Edge Platform**. This component shall provide a wide range of automation services, which will be used and extended to support CODECO requirements, namely:
 - **Near Edge data integration via ETSI Multi-Access Control (MEC) API support**, which relies on ETSI-proposed MEC Platform services³⁵, to provide near Edge networking (e.g., network quality, UE location, channel information) Within NetMA, the MEC API services will offer integrated network KPIs such as device's location, channel information, while it will also fuse those KPIs with information's brought to CODECO components via ALTO to create a consolidated and unified view over network capabilities and restrictions.

30 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/alto/about/>

31 <http://l2sm.io>

32 <https://www.edgexfoundry.org/>

33 <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.edc>

34 <https://argoproj.github.io/argo-workflows/>

35 <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/multi-access-edge-computing>

- **Far Edge data integration via EdgeX.** The π -edge platform encompasses IoT services as it is integrated with the EdgeX Foundry³⁶. Via this component, NetMA shall be able to bring far Edge data into CODECO components.
- **Network state forecasting.** This NetMA sub-component will oversee the continuous monitoring and provisioning of the network status to prevent and restore abnormalities. Network KPIs offered by MEC services and ALTO will be collected and aggregated for applying forecasting methods, while it will also interact with PDCL component. This interfacing will allow NetMA to consider PDLC outputs generated by complex prediction, optimization, and estimation DL models regarding network infrastructure status.
- **Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controller.** It is a centralized software application that manages and controls network devices in an SDN architecture. It handles network topology, traffic flows, and device configurations. The controller will typically communicate with devices through protocols like NETCONF, providing network monitoring and management functions. It enables centralized management, network policies, traffic engineering, and automation, making it easier to manage large and complex networks. The SDN controller can help NetMA to deploy the programmable network connectivity interconnections. A challenge to solve in CODECO-like scenarios is the potential technological diversity that can be found in the diverse network domains that can form the network footprint. In this sense it is yet under analysis the role of the SDN controller within NetMA. A primary approach is to consider the SDN controller as the element for programmatically configuring a connectivity overlay that can permit to overcome the limitations due to handle different technological domains connecting the edge and cloud nodes forming the compute domain. Thus, the primary role identified is the one of controlling the connectivity endpoints (i.e., the entry points of the traffic flows), leveraging on overlay tunnelled solutions for traversing the distinct network domains. Further work and analysis will be performed during the project lifetime so that the role of the SDN controller could evolved (e.g., by leveraging in local SDN controllers per domain for traffic engineering purposes).
- **L2S-M.** Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms (L2S-M) has been identified as the basic connectivity mechanism for CODECO. L2S-M provides a K8s networking solution that complements the Container Network Interface (CNI) plugin approach, enabling the creation and management of virtual networks in K8s clusters. These virtual networks allow workloads (pods) to have isolated link-layer (or layer-2) connectivity with other pods within a K8s cluster (i.e., intra-cluster communications), regardless of the K8s node where they are deployed. L2S-M enables the creation/deletion of virtual networks on-demand, as well as attaching/detaching pods to those networks. L2S-M uses a programmable data-plane based on SDN, which in turn provides a high degree of flexibility to dynamically incorporate new application and/or network configurations into K8s clusters. The main K8s interface of pods remains intact (provided by a CNI plugin), retaining the compatibility with all the standard K8s elements (e.g., services, connectivity through the main interface). Following a similar model, L2S-M can be used to support inter-cluster communications and enable the connectivity in scenarios where pods may span across multiple distributed infrastructures. To this purpose, L2S-M operates a link-layer overlay network among different clusters and leverages an SDN-based inter-domain connectivity orchestrator to handle the communications through that overlay. This OSI Layer 2 overlay approach provides some advantages in an environment such as CODECO, for instance in terms of transparency regarding the underlying transport technology or independence of the IP addressing for the establishment of services across clusters of different administrative domains. The code for the inter-cluster

³⁶ <https://www.edgexfoundry.org/>

communications is pending to be published as open-source in the L2S-M repository over the next few months.

- Metadata embedding.** One of the ambitions to explore in the NetMA component is the possibility of handling metadata related to the networking aspects. Approaches for adding or embedding metadata on the traffic flows will be analysed as part of the connectivity solution used, since there is a dependency on the way of realizing the encapsulation of traffic flows. Examples for metadata that can be embedded has as starting point the metrics presented in Annex I. To add or embed Metadata on the traffic flows we are going to need some mechanisms that will depend on the connectivity solution used as it will be part of the way we realize the encapsulation. Currently, three possible solutions are: Network Service Header, MD-Type 1 Data Center Allocation Schema and MD-Type 2 TLV.

Figure 21: ALTO as network exposure function of the network.

2.4.5.4 Interfaces

The current interfaces of NetMA to other CODECO components, identified in Figure 20, are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: NetMA interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-ACM-NET-1	Integration of the NetMA CRD/CR(s) and respective operator(s)	CRD	Input
I-SWM-NET-1	Used to request NetMA to perform QoS reservations. SWM may perform requests for reservations to NetMA, based on the scheduling/placement decisions. Furthermore, NetMA may also handle network related CRs (<i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i>) to reflect network conditions.	CR	Bi-directional
I-NET-PDLC-1	Request infrastructure estimation	CR	Input

2.4.5.5 Generic Operation Example for One Cluster

During the setup of an application deployment (rf. to section 2.3.1.1), NetMA is activated by ACM, and triggers the definition of the network overlay through the policies and requirements received (ACM, SWM), passing the overlay information to SWM (IP, DNS/namespace configuration). This information feeds the PDLC to perform its initial multi-objective estimations, which it will be passed to the ACM to perform the initial configuration process readjustments.

Once this phase is complete, the system enters in the cluster runtime phase (rf. to section 2.3.1.2). In this phase, ACM readjusts the configuration according to the input it receives, activating NetMA (as well as the other modules) to perform a redistribution of the workload between layers. This will be an iterative process that will be performed periodically as needed by the system, adjusting the behaviour according to the readjustments to be considered at each moment of operation.

In the initial configuration phase (one cluster), the L2S-M sub-component will provide secure connectivity among Pods deployed across worker nodes within the cluster, regardless the specific compute nodes involved in the workload deployment. To this purpose, L2S-M supports the flexible creation of virtual networks in the cluster, and the attachment of workload to those virtual networks. Likewise, L2S-M will support the connectivity of workloads towards external networks, i.e., the Internet.

2.4.5.6 Considerations for Federated Clusters

At NetMA we are going to work in multi-domain environments, so the issue of federated communications is something we must consider. To provide a specific example of operation, we rely on a CDN example which shall be addressed in CODECO as one of the use-cases (use-case P2, rf. to Deliverable D8). Figure 20 depicts an illustration of CDN deployment across a multi-cluster environment, where 6 different regions are considered (CD-x represents a region), based on four types of networking technology (represented as arrows of different colours).

To achieve this federation, NetMA shall use the capacity of L2S-M to support the creation of inter-domain virtual networks. These networks allow for link-layer communications among workloads deployed on different clusters. L2S-M creates an overlay network of layer-2 switches, with one switch deployed as a workload on each cluster. The NetMA will include specific components to monitor the network performance metrics among clusters (e.g., bandwidth, delay, jitter). These metrics will be used to create cost-maps that reflect the costs of the inter-cluster communication alternatives. Cost-maps will be exposed through ALTO to all CODECO architectural components. In particular, the L2S-M sub-component of NetMA will leverage this information to construct an efficient overlay network and determine appropriate policies for workload traffic distribution on top of it.

Figure 22: High-level example of NetMA operation for federated clusters.

3 CODECO Technological Guidelines

Orchestration aspects across the Edge-Cloud continuum are being addressed by several initiatives across Europe, following different approaches and relying on different technologies. The approach considered by CODECO, that takes into consideration an Edge-Cloud continuum adaptation based on compute, network and data resources, integrates advanced concepts in comparison to current state-of-the-art. This section explains with further detail the different CODECO contributions, explaining the CODECO technological guidelines and decisions made in the first six months of the project regarding open-source technology adopted, relying on related literature and towards other *Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs)* under the topic HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01. The section starts with an overview on the key contributions, then addresses potential synergies with other RIAs, and concludes with a summary of technological guidelines.

3.1 CODECO Contributions

CODECO contributes to the following research topics: i) automated configuration, ii) dynamic scheduling and workload mitigation, iii) context awareness and decentralised learning, iv) infrastructure adaptation based on cross-layer data-compute-network approach, and v) data as a resource. The advances beyond state of the art, which are explained next, are being materialized into the CODECO framework and its individual components, which have been explained in section 2.

3.1.1 Automated Configuration

Aiming to provide concrete setup, configuration, and synchronization mechanisms suitable for federated cluster environments, CODECO integrates ACM, which offers automated management mechanisms to support both cluster configuration and application deployment setup, runtime workflows, and resource management (i.e., considering also non-k8s environments), and, at the same time, to assure minimum human intervention. To this end,

CODECO leverages and extends well-established open-source solutions that facilitate efficient and automated multi-cluster deployment and lifecycle management.

Fully automated cluster setup is currently well-supported by K8s-native solutions; two such prominent solutions are KubeSpray³⁷ and kOps³⁸, although they are intended for single-cluster deployments. Existing multi-clustering solutions (e.g., Karmada³⁹, Ligo⁴⁰, OCM) are commonly adopting a declarative management model in the control plane. For instance, KubeVela⁴¹ recently emerged as a modern software delivery and management control plane that uses a declarative syntax to define applications in a single manifest file. It declares deployment plans as workflows and runs them automatically through customized, so-called topology policies that enable application delivery across multiple clusters. Overall, most multi-cluster management solutions are focused on hybrid Cloud environments and cover emerging Edge-to-Cloud scenarios to a lesser extent, only. In fact, several lightweight Kubernetes derivatives have been developed (e.g., K3s⁴², K0s⁴³, MicroShift⁴⁴) to handle the specific requirements of the far Edge and have been compared in terms of different performance aspects [22].

There are also K8s-based or other platforms leveraging K8s designed for the Edge, such as KubeEdge⁴⁵, KubeOne^{46,47}, and Open Horizon⁴⁸, each one focusing on aspects, e.g., resource consumption, device computational power. Particularly for scalability, when scaling needs to be performed quickly and in an event-driven manner, serverless deployment using solutions such as Knative⁴⁹, is another efficient method to react and scale resources rapidly. Furthermore, kcp⁵⁰ is a multi-tenant solution that fits requirements of Edge-Cloud deployment, e.g., their resource constraints and heterogeneity. kcp offers a K8s-like control plane, aimed at supporting many independent, isolated “clusters” called workspaces.

Despite the recent advancements in multi-cluster systems, most approaches cope just partially, or anyway not sufficiently with the challenges posed by the Edge-Cloud continuum paradigm, such as providing seamless end-to-end interconnection, handling device or communication protocol heterogeneity, while still, tackling scalability and elasticity issues that hinder their application in Edge-to-Cloud setups.

Aiming to fill this gap, and as has been explained in section 2.4.1, CODECO has opted to rely on OCM and on the RHT OCM upstream project ACM. Both tools are based on RHT K8s distribution OpenShift⁵¹, which is a mature alternative to the canonical K8s⁵². OpenShift is a very mature technology that has edged over its competing solutions, especially in production environments; this is mostly because OpenShift ensures high availability and uptime. Other OpenShift-related projects have evolved to support Edge scenarios. Hypershift is a solution that ensures scalability and fast provisioning of K8s clusters in remote/Edge worker nodes. MicroShift is a lightweight Kubernetes solution for deploying solely a minimal OpenShift control plane. To meet the strict requirements of even more constrained

37 <https://github.com/kubernetes-sigs/kubespray>

38 <https://github.com/kubernetes/kops>

39 <https://karmada.io/>

40 <https://liqo.io/>

41 <https://kubevela.io/>

42 <https://www.rancher.com/products/k3s>

43 <https://k0sproject.io/>

44 <https://github.com/openshift/microshift>

45 <https://kubedge.io/en/>

46 <https://www.kubermatic.com/products/kubermatic-kubernetes-platform/>

47 <https://www.kubermatic.com/products/kubermatic-kubeone/edge/>

48 <https://www.lfedge.org/projects/openhorizon/>

49 <https://knative.dev/docs/>

50 <https://github.com/kcp-dev/kcp>

51 <https://www.redhat.com/en/technologies/cloud-computing/openshift/container-platform>

52 <https://ubuntu.com/kubernetes/compare>

environments, such as far Edge requirements, there are other evolving approaches, such as Flotta which integrates nicely with Microshift.

CODECO is designed to add value to a number of those technologies (e.g., OCM, Flotta, KCP, Knative) by extending them to support multi-clustering and resource management at the Edge, efficiently, and cover novel Cloud-to-Edge use cases, explicitly. To evaluate the ability of the CODECO framework to address the specific requirements of such use-cases, the technical advances provided by CODECO, including ACM performance, will be extensively evaluated in real-world experiments (WP5).

The experimental facilities to be developed from M7 onwards (WP5) comprise local testbeds shared among partners and public Cloud shared resources, along with the global EdgeNet testbed. The first phase of experimentation in CODECO (until M18) relates with one cluster operations only and hence, the scalability of multi-cluster environments is not an issue. For the second part of the project, the available infrastructure is expected to be able to scale in accordance with the expected project KPIs.

3.1.2 Dynamic Scheduling and Workload Migration

Existing scheduling and workload migration mechanisms address synchronization issues in single-cluster settings and with respect to some aspects. For example, the Intel *Telemetry Aware Scheduler for Service Healing and Platform Resilience* (TAS) [23] supports telemetry-aware scheduling and intelligent placement of workloads as a K8s plugin. TAS enforces a rule-based, user defined telemetry policy on the cluster to influence Pod placement, taking into consideration compute node health metrics. Also, the lightweight *Kubernetes-based Event Driven Autoscaler (KEDA)*⁵³ allows calling Pods based on external events and triggers, thus providing the basis to extend the capability of native K8s autoscaling between CPU and memory. KubeSphere⁵⁴ is a widely known scheduling mechanism in hybrid multi-clouds that works as a middleware component in a K8s cluster and, periodically, dispatches tasks to connected K8s clusters based on custom defined policies and fairness goals. Thus, KubeSphere eliminates the need for K8s to keep tasks on hold to be scheduled later [24]. An overview of the available K8s scheduling approaches can be found in a recent survey [25].

Nevertheless, scheduling solutions are constrained by the inherent lack of network-related insights in the scheduling decisions. CODECO advances beyond the state-of-the-art by incorporating **different categories of data (data-compute-network)** and **context-awareness** in the scheduling loop as has been debated in section 2.4.4. To this end, one promising starting point is the K8s plugin Network-aware scheduler [26] which enables latency- and bandwidth-aware Pod (co-)scheduling by considering properties of both application and infrastructure network topology in scheduling decisions having as key target purpose latency reduction. To achieve the latter, it establishes network weights between regions and zones in the cluster. Thus, network aspects are considered in scheduling K8s Pods by pre-ordering the node list according to connectivity with already scheduled Pods. The scheduler also uses a bandwidth resource component to advertise egress bandwidth as extended resource to allow already available filter/scoring plugins to also consider bandwidth allocation. However, there are some known limitations associated with this scheduler, which impact the technical implementation. More specifically, we note: (i) the absence of a dedicated controller (e.g., like ⁵⁵) to react to node additions, updates, or removals, to handle the bandwidth allocatable in each region or zone, and also to update the network weights based on real-time latency measurements, and (ii) the limitations of the scheduler that introduces a custom plugin which makes use of the QueueSort extension point and thus, it cannot be

⁵³<https://keda.sh/>

⁵⁴ <https://kubesphere.io/>

⁵⁵ <https://github.com/jpedro1992/network-topology-controller>

combined with other plugins that access the same extension point. In addition, scheduling is still sequential per Pod, which leads to the possibility of blocking decisions and deadlocks. When federated clusters are considered, there are further challenges that need to be addressed. Multi-cluster systems currently lack concrete co-scheduling mechanisms, and only very recently, new synchronization mechanisms have been proposed, including K8s Sigs Co scheduling plugin⁵⁶, which is still in beta status, Admiralty⁵⁷ and the no-longer-maintained k8s-spark-scheduler⁵⁸, and also the recent research efforts RLSK [27][27], Twine [28].

In this context, CODECO explicitly targets synchronization issues in multi-cluster environments. Building upon the notion of Seamless computing [30], the CODECO SWM component (rf. to section 2.4.3) will contribute to the state-of-the-art by providing advanced scheduling, as well as workload orchestration and migration.

As of now, Seamless computing is premised on a comprehensive QoS model [31] that considers application requirements and infrastructure capabilities (compute, storage, network) to optimize the deployment of the distributed applications across Edge-Cloud.

In CODECO, SWM will extend the current Seamless computing implementation by considering not only the information provided by the QoS model, but also contextual information related to users, data, and/or the infrastructure specifications, as has been explained in sections 2.4.3 and 2.4.4.

In addition, CODECO will leverage SWM to facilitate the workload migration in challenging cases, such as in highly heterogeneous environments with requirements per cluster, in mobile networks with intermittent connectivity wherein nodes join or leave the network frequently, as well as in scenarios with mobile far Edge nodes that require automated remote reconfiguration of computing and data processing modules.

Finally, SWM will extend seamless computing by integrating estimations provided by PDLC (ML/DL decentralised, on-demand approaches) to enable well-informed scheduling and migration decisions. SWM will, not only, interoperate with advanced ML and decentralised learning approaches from which it will be getting input, but also exploit such algorithms for itself while making scheduling decisions. This feature is quite novel and allows for supporting scheduling and workload migration, especially in federated clusters.

3.1.3 Context-awareness and Privacy-Preserving Decentralised Learning

Context-awareness has been effectively integrated into the edge-cloud continuum [32][33][34] enhancing network automation and adaptation. However, in dynamic and highly heterogeneous environments, such as IoT, a fresh approach is necessary to tackle significant limitations [35] including: i) the small subset of available indicators typically used to infer behaviour, instead of a larger and richer set of indicators; ii) the wide variety of highly interconnected devices and data types involved; iii) limitations related to computational and data exchange capabilities, especially on resource-constrained devices, and iv) the lack of knowledge related to all the necessary context dimensions.

The use of context-awareness to provide a more flexible orchestration across Edge-Cloud is a topic in recent literature. For instance, a debate on the use of context-awareness has been provided by Ogbuachi et al. in the context of Edge-based applications across a 5G infrastructure [39]. The authors defined context as cluster and network data that should be integrated into the K8s scheduler, proposing a measure of usability of a node. Specifically,

56 <https://github.com/kubernetes-sigs/scheduler-plugins/tree/master/pkg/coscheduling>

57 <https://github.com/admiraltyio/admiralty>

58 <https://github.com/palantir/k8s-spark-scheduler>

their algorithm, which has been shown to improve the behaviour in comparison to K8s, relies on collected node (e.g., CPU, memory) and network data (e.g., network delay) and current workload, as well as requirements of the applications, to propose an adaptation while preserving fairness in terms of workload distribution. Kaur et al. propose a multi-objective scheduling optimization based on integer linear programming, KEIDS [40], which aims at minimizing the energy usage for IIoT environments. Context is defined in their work as node energy usage, carbon footprint emissions and performance interference, and their algorithm shows relevant performance improvements in terms of energy consumption efficiency in comparison to existing K8s schedulers, based on real-time Google traces. Energy and latency, along with specific node usage indicators such as CPU and memory, are the most common context indicators considered in elastic orchestration.

However, there are other relevant context indicators that can be sensed across the supported system, going beyond network and application requirements, as has been proposed by Silva et al. [35].

In what concerns behaviour learning and inference, AI/ML is bringing significant benefits to several Edge and Cloud applications, enabling fast and autonomous decision-making [36]. However, the conventional model of centralized learning brings in challenges to the new types of Edge-Cloud environments, integrating mobility and resource constrained devices, as in centralized ML architecture patterns, the data training occurs at a central location, usually in the Cloud. Large bulks of data need to be transferred, and this implies having a resilient infrastructure, that can support in parallel many data sources, which introduce significant challenges related to latency, energy efficiency, privacy/security, and the adaptability of models to dynamic data structure [37].

Decentralised learning relies on a multi-node approach, where datasets are locally trained (per node). Decentralised learning engages the server to distribute a pre-trained or generic ML model to the participating entities. Decentralised Learning is particularly beneficial when there are frequent and large updates of data, and eventually, some devices are resource constrained - hence, distributed learning approaches become beneficial in Edge-Cloud environments [36] as the ones supported in CODECO. Decentralised learning can bring in benefits such as: i) reduced latency and bandwidth consumption by minimizing raw data transmissions, ii) distributed and asymmetric model training, e.g., applying different models to utilize local sensor data effectively, iii) enhanced security/privacy, minimizing data leakage risk, and iv) efficient computational load distribution across the Edge.

Although the adoption of DL approaches on the emerging network paradigm is garnering increasing interest, it brings forth significant challenges related to crucial aspects like mobility, communication/computational heterogeneity, and security/privacy [36][37]. For example, most of the existing works consider unrealistic assumptions for the underlying data structures of the Edge devices or secure and high throughput connection among the edge and core devices. Even in the more recent framework of *federated learning (FL)* [37] current literature focuses on improving the convergence of learning time without considering limitations related to the wireless communication channel or devices' energy restrictions. An exception is debated by Housseinalipour et al. in [37], where the trade-off between the communication/computational characteristics, and, the energy consumption of the edge nodes and the accuracy/convergence time of the learning algorithm are jointly studied, through novel optimization models. Similarly, an FL approach considering communication restrictions has been introduced by McMahan et al [42]. While Wang et al propose a model compression technique to meet the resource availability and the computational/storage limitations of the edge nodes, however, without considering the time-varying performance (e.g., communication/computational/energy) across the nodes [43]. Besides heterogeneity, existing FL designs are demonstrated to be vulnerable to threats or attacks; a comprehensive review is given in [38].

A recent evolution of decentralised, privacy preserving learning is Swarm learning⁵⁹, built on the principles of *Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)*. Raw data is kept local, while learning parameters are shared via a swarm network - hence, models are built independently at the Edge. Swarm Learning integrates security to support data sovereignty, confidentiality, via smart contracts involving on pre-authorized participants. Swarm learning therefore supports a dynamic onboarding of nodes, via smart contracts. Once a new node enters (via a smart contract), it obtains a model and performs local training until specific synchronization conditions are met. Then, the model parameters are exchange via a swarm API, and merged to create an updated model with updated parameter settings before a new training round is started.

CODECO builds on the integration of context-awareness and privacy-preserving decentralised learning, proposing as core of the orchestration PDLC (rf. to section 2.4.4).

PDLC integrates a context-awareness sub-component (PDLC-CA) responsible for metrics collection (based on existing K8 API and its extensions) and preparation/aggregation. A second sub-component, PDLC-DL focuses on decentralised training, learning, and corresponding outputs (e.g., estimation, detection, optimization, and prediction). PDLC acts as a recommendation system injecting its outputs to other CODECO components, e.g., SWM, ACM, and not as a decision-making mechanism. In a nutshell, PDLC offers the following major contributions: i) cross-layer operation exploiting a wide range of input parameters, ii) automated deployment/orchestration of edge-based services, supporting elastic models re-adaptable to context changes and specific service requirements, and iii) joint orchestration of data, compute and network resources based on novel privacy-preserving decentralised learning techniques.

The context-awareness sub-component utilizes various indicators from different sources to enhance its functionality in dynamic edge-cloud environments, spanning from user (e.g., visits per IP or location), system (e.g., energy/resource consumption), data (e.g., data compliance) and application/network (e.g., network QoS) behaviour through-to nodes behaviour (e.g., health status). Given the high amount of raw data, PDLC provides a novel pre-processing procedure, capable to perform: i) data clearance and instability check (e.g., outlier detection [44] or change-point analysis [45]), ii) clustering, feature extraction and similarity measures, supporting both linear (e.g., k-Means, PCA) or non-linear (e.g., kernel based) techniques, based on the data-dependencies being categorized through statistical tools, e.g., dHSIC. Here, the employment of the pre-processing step is twofold, i.e., extract meaningful information that may support re-adjustments, nodes selection for FL execution or data labelling and complexity reduction concluding on a feasible data handling.

Focusing on the advancements in the learning component, PDLC provides a decentralised learning framework that incorporates recent concepts from FL [46]. More precisely, we focus on: i) adaptive processes that consider the requirements and restrictions of the overall CODECO components, incorporating learning architectures, similar to state of the art approaches [48]; ii) cross-layer intelligence without the need to share raw data between different nodes and clusters; iii) privacy-preserving intelligence across the Edge-Cloud continuum, complement to existing works, such as [51][51][52]. Furthermore, Song et al introduce an efficient privacy-preserving data aggregation mechanism for FL that aggregates users trained models secretly without leaking the user's model.

Here, we give particular attention to methods such as SplitNN [55] and Swarm Learning [55][56]. Emphasizing on swarm-based intelligence, PDLC enables the synthesis of solutions

⁵⁹ <https://github.com/HewlettPackard/swarm-learning>

through decentralised self-organized agents that autonomously operate based on local information, also contributing to the global optimization through their participation in the swarm network. Furthermore, PDLC offers multi-cluster operation support [60] where the swarm-node(s) acts as the controller(s) responsible for centralized model training/retraining, while the workers are responsible for local model execution/prediction; enriching the traditional FL framework, which assumes a single exclusive data center with limited coordination among multiple FL workers providing their gradients centrally to the FL server. Note that, the latter is strongly related to the MARL approach, which considers the cooperation of multiple agents, implementing a federated learning concept to maximize the global reward. In this context, PDLC exploits the employment of hybrid learning architectures that combine different ML techniques according to the use-case or the system requirements, as denoted in the work by Turina et al. [61][61]. In [61] Turina et al propose a hybrid federated Split learning architecture is proposed to combine the benefits of several ML approaches in terms of efficiency and privacy.

Finally, we outline a set of potential future challenges, such as, i) limitation on the storage and computational capacity of the participated nodes of the federated learning, ii) performance instabilities due to the “curse of dimensionality” or the “black swan effect”, and iii) issues related to the labelling and the structure of the training data.

3.1.4 Cross-layer Network Adaptation

CODECO proposes the NetMA component to handle the K8s underlay network for application deployments across Edge-Cloud. Some important aspects of NetMA which have been debated in section 2.4.5 include the: (i) network connectivity and communication using CNI plugins; (ii) interconnection of diverse Edge-Cloud environments and across federated clusters; (iii) exposure/provisioning of network information towards other CODECO components based on the ALTO protocol; and (iv) integration of AI/ML techniques to forecast network behaviour.

In containerized applications CNI plugins are responsible for providing networking capabilities to containerized environments, typically in the context of container orchestration platforms. Combined with K8s, CNI integrates with Kubelet, enabling an overlay or underlay network to automatically configure the network between pods. A list of CNI plugins for cluster networking based on the CNCF ecosystem landscape include Calico⁶⁰, Flannel⁶¹, Weave (Net)⁶², Cilium⁶³, Canal⁶⁴, Antrea⁶⁵, Kube-OVN⁶⁶, OVN-K⁶⁷ and Multus⁶⁸. CNI solutions support various network models (Overlay, Underlay, Hybrid) as well as utilize several tunneling options (e.g., *Virtual Extensible LAN*, VXLAN⁶⁹; UDP; IPsec; GRE; *Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation*, Geneve [64], Host-GW, Weave Mesh) with some of them supporting additional features such as multicasting, encryption, IPv6, IPVS/LVS, (Linux) bridging and eBPF. Although none of the available CNI plugins is universally superior, performance comparisons can be found in related [65][66][67][67] arguing that Flannel and Weave produce lower overhead, while Calico, Cilium, Kube-OVN and OVN-K offer more advanced features at the cost of overhead.

CODECO plans to rely on the OVN-K network plugin (also used by Microshift) which is the default network provider for the OpenShift Container Platform, implemented as a set of K8s controllers and CRs. It uses *Open Virtual Network (OVN)* as the networking backend,

60 <https://github.com/projectcalico/calico>

61 <https://github.com/flannel-io/flannel>

62 <https://github.com/weaveworks/weave>

63 <https://github.com/cilium/cilium>

64 <https://github.com/projectcalico/canal>

65 <https://github.com/antrea-io/antrea>

66 <https://github.com/kubeovn/kube-ovn>

67 <https://github.com/ovn-org/ovn-kubernetes>

68 <https://github.com/k8snetworkplumbingwg/multus-cni>

69 <https://networklessons.com/cisco/ccnp-encor-350-401/introduction-to-virtual-extensible-lan-vxlan>

providing an overlay-based networking implementation and K8s-specific APIs for managing the network traffic flows. It runs a daemon on each node and uses the Geneve protocol rather than VXLAN to create an overlay network between nodes. In addition, NetMA will utilize the *Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms* (L2S-M) [67] solution, a K8s operator that enables virtual networking in K8s clusters to manage virtual networks and pods to those networks. L2S-M complements/extends the CNI plugin approach of K8s, treating virtual networks as Multus CRDs. The advantages of L2S-M compared to other CNI plugins lie in the establishment of an SDN based programmable data plane (using virtual switches based on OVS) which allows network paths to be established by a variety of algorithms (e.g., reactive, metric-based, geographic-based), as well as allowing services to react in advance to changes and select the most appropriate paths without tampering with their network layer configuration [64]. Thus, it provides high flexibility to incorporate new applications into K8s clusters, in a dynamic way.

Other solutions implement direct networking between K8s clusters (on-premises or in the cloud) include Skupper⁷⁰ and Submariner⁷¹, which can be utilized with service meshes, such as Istio⁷². In microservice architectures, a service mesh is a dedicated infrastructure layer on top of the network layer provided by CNI plugins - typically implemented as a scalable set of network proxies (usually Envoy⁷³) - that controls service-to-service communication over a network, handling network traffic and enforcing policies between these services. Some popular service mesh implementations include Istio⁷⁴, Consul⁷⁵, Linkerd⁷⁶, Kuma⁷⁷, Traefik Mesh⁷⁸ and AWS App Mesh⁷⁹. Both Skupper and Submariner tools aim to simplify networking in multi-cluster K8s environments and enabling seamless communication and connectivity across clusters, while they can integrate various container network plugins (Flannel, Calico, Cilium) to leverage their underlying networking capabilities and extend them for multi-cluster connectivity. While Skupper primarily focuses on enabling bidirectional communication and service discovery between clusters, Submariner focuses on establishing secure connections, providing unified IP address spaces and network routing between clusters.

The deployment and interconnection of applications across such distributed and heterogeneous environments in the Edge-Cloud is a significant challenge.

The CODECO's NetMA component will support the interconnection of diverse Edge-Cloud environments (e.g., wireless, cellular, fixed networks), handling the setup of interconnections in an automated way which is required for a flexible operation.

NetMA will handle internal and external applications as ALTO clients. ALTO [69][4] is an ongoing standardization protocol which refers to a fundamental problem of P2P applications: the lack of sufficient reliable knowledge of the underlying network infrastructure. It exposes network information (e.g., network topology, link bandwidth) towards components/applications, allowing for well-reasoned/informed connection decisions in situations of service redundancy. The key abstractions of ALTO are network and cost maps which allow network-aware optimizations such as path selection (peer & server selection) and job scheduling to optimize the overall network traffic and performance while reducing congestion probability.

70 <https://github.com/skupperproject/skupper> , <https://skupper.io/>

71 <https://github.com/submariner-io/submariner> , <https://submariner.io/>

72 <https://cloud.redhat.com/blog/set-up-an-istio-multicluster-service-mesh-with-submariner-in-red-hat-advanced-cluster-management-for-kubernetes>

73 <https://github.com/envoyproxy/envoy> , <https://www.envoyproxy.io/>

74 <https://github.com/istio/istio> , <https://istio.io/>

75 <https://github.com/hashicorp/consul-k8s>

76 <https://github.com/linkerd/linkerd2> , <https://linkerd.io/>

77 <https://github.com/kumahq/kuma> , <https://kuma.io/>

78 <https://github.com/traefik/mesh> , <https://traefik.io/traefik-mesh/>

79 <https://github.com/aws/aws-app-mesh-examples>

CODECO NetMA will also integrate AI/ML techniques to predict the behaviour of networking KPIs, perform adaptive control and address real-time readjustment by communicating with the AI/ML engine in CODECO, PDLC.

Regarding the CODECO limitations, challenges due to the decentralization in Edge environments might need to be handled; for example: (i) additional overhead; (ii) performance balancing and isolation; (iii) additional requirements integration (e.g., data locality, network requirements).

3.1.5 Data as a Resource

The extreme growth of data generation, IoT and Edge-Cloud computing and the advent of AI/ML have elevated data management as an increasing priority. CODECO aspires to overcome emerging challenges regarding security, privacy, regulation, and decision-making that leverages data from various components across cloud, edge, and multiple K8s clusters, based on the novel CODECO component MDM.

Data management evolved from an ad hoc storing of data in file systems, databases or cloud object stores adapted to local needs to organization-level storing of data in data warehouses [71][72] (e.g., structured, filter data), data lakes [73][74][75] (e.g., raw unstructured or multi-structured data) and influenced notions such as data lagoons [76] or data lakehouses [77][78]. However, the latter are characterized by inflexibility to adapt to changing demands (i.e., the structured approaches), privacy or regulation issues (especially in the case of multi-domain or multi-cluster deployments) and scalability/performance issues.

Metadata management systems, like data meshes [79]^{80,81} and data fabrics [80][81], emerged to mitigate these issues based primarily on data catalogues found on cloud or on-premises systems. They operate in a distributed manner, process data locally and publish them to centralized metadata catalogues. The stored metadata can then be discovered from diverse distributed components. Existing metadata management systems are being manifested as single data processing systems rather than on large-scale systems with heterogeneous data from different/distributed environments (e.g., collecting meta-data across clusters) and cross-organizations. Furthermore, there is a recent trend towards advanced cloud service catalogues, such as Gaia-X [84], providing secure data sharing at scale, in a compliant way based on real-time data observability/monitoring and processing tools.

Observability-based data management brings significant privacy, scalability, and performance advantages since it collects metadata centrally rather than data. Additionally, connectors interface to local data systems and generate events when significant changes occur. Therefore, data management can react to those changes and not rely on repeatedly polling external systems to stay up to date, although additional mechanisms (such as timer-based events to occasionally refresh data) are not precluded to make the system more robust.

In CODECO, the data management is achieved through the deployment of MDM, of which the core is an Enterprise Data Map, i.e., a real-time updated graph which gathers diverse and extensible sources of metadata [85].

MDM provides the basis for distributed data management through an extendable connector model, which is used to interface to distributed systems and gather information about the stored data. The scalability is ensured since connectors can be developed for new and legacy data systems, while datasets stored in existing file systems or newer types of DMS can be incorporated including cloud offerings (e.g., Snowflake⁸² that provides "data-as-a-service"). Furthermore, multiple connectors can report information on the same dataset. One connector can integrate directly to the data stores to discover existing datasets as well as the structure

80 <https://www.datamesh-architecture.com/>

81 <https://www.ibm.com/topics/data-mesh>

82 <https://www.snowflake.com/en/>

(schema) of the data. Additional connectors can gather information from existing data catalogues to discover configured data, and different connectors can interface to systems that analyse datasets to automatically determine data characteristics (e.g., quality, sensitivity).

CODECO operators can be deployed throughout the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum, and in on-premises data domains to ensure that all data is visible to the CODECO framework components and use cases alike. CODECO extends the value of global data observability by exploiting this in the service orchestration platform. Orchestration decisions can incorporate data issues (performance, compliance) in addition to classic metrics such as server utilization and network performance as well as be taken across clusters based on the globally available metadata.

Regarding CODECO limitations, the strict rules, and regulations for data due to GDPR should be considered. Such privacy issues for UCs include the hesitation/denial from authorities for the collection and usage of data (e.g., video, images from public transportation) either raw data or processed. Other issues include the management of security-related metadata such as user access control and encryption settings, as well as restrictions related to the rights for the content and to the geographical location.

3.2 Potential synergies with HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01 call projects

Although indeed some objectives are overlapping between our project and projects funded under the same call topic (DEDICE⁸³, CloudSkin⁸⁴, COGNIFOG⁸⁵), e.g., automated setup and configuration, adaptive scheduling and workload placement, network-awareness, each project addresses the challenges of the Cloud-to-Edge continuum in a different way. CODECO seeks to bring innovation regarding the five above-presented key topics, still complementing the work of other projects.

The expertise gained during CODECO, and the developed technological assets could be enhanced by integrating advancements provided by other projects. That way, additional aspects that are not considered in CODECO can be incorporated and hence, there might be potential to overcome technological boundaries identified in our project.

For instance, several projects focus on data mining, providing federated data pools, trustworthy data sharing, data analytics or data monetization. Here, MDM component can be interconnected with the data collected by FAME⁸⁶ or EXA4MIND⁸⁷. Moreover, there might be room for collaboration, especially in specific use cases. For example, CODECO could exploit the toolset expected to be provided by EMERALDS⁸⁸ for gathering large mobility data streams in the smart city use case. Of course, considering it the other way round, projects focused on data management could evaluate their project results using the CODECO EdgeNet framework. In a similar fashion, synergies could be formed in the context of decentralised learning, e.g., with OpenSwarm⁸⁹ for energy-aware swarm intelligence.

3.3 Summary, CODECO Technological Guidelines

In summary, this section discussed the main technological guidelines to be introduced to address the research goals of CODECO. To this end, we highlighted the major CODECO

83 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101092582>

84 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101092646>

85 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101092968>

86 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101092639>

87 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101092944>

88 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093051>

89 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093046>

contributes on the above research topics: i) automated configuration, ii) dynamic scheduling and workload mitigation, iii) context awareness and decentralised learning, iv) infrastructure adaptation based on cross-layer data-compute-network approach, and v) data as a resource, which reflect the main functionalities of CODECO. Finally, potential collaborative opportunities with relevant HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01 call projects are explored.

4 Global Validation Aspects

As an open-source framework, CODECO shall provide extensive experimentation and validation of its components, of the overall framework, or of aspects thereof. In this section, we provide guidelines for experimentation (WP5).

4.1 Experimentation Tools and Guidelines

4.1.1 Simulators, Emulators, Testbeds

In this subsection, we propose some important experimentation tools that can be utilized for the validation of the different CODECO technologies and components.

Several emulators and simulators can be used to test Edge-Cloud components of CODECO, e.g., node containers and networking aspects. For instance, Mininet-WiFi⁹⁰ (useful to simulate Edge devices), Containernet⁹¹ (useful for lightweight Edge-Cloud) and OpenConfig-KNE⁹² (a K8s network emulation) can create custom network topologies and add container-based hosts, while simulators such as k8s-netsim⁹³ (a Mininet based K8s Network Simulator) simulates K8s workers as Mininet hosts (using flannel for connectivity among containers and Skupper for multi-cluster deployments). Furthermore, additional network simulators and emulators can be utilized to investigate independent/isolated network mechanisms, technologies, and standards (e.g., cloud deployments, TSN) such as CORE⁹⁴, EMANE⁹⁵, EstiNet⁹⁶, OMNeT++⁹⁷ and ns-3⁹⁸.

Some tools utilized for benchmarking in K8s include kubestr⁹⁹ - a set of tools to evaluate the performance of cluster storage options, kube-bench¹⁰⁰ - a tool to evaluate the K8s deployment security, k-bench¹⁰¹ - a framework for benchmarking the control and data plane aspects of a K8s infrastructure (Pod start, networking, I/O metrics), Theodolite¹⁰² - a framework for benchmarking the horizontal and vertical scalability of cloud-native K8s applications/microservices. In addition, basic tools such as iPerf, JMeter, cURL, and wget can be used for various aspects of networking, workload, and performance testing. In the context of K8s, iPerf server and client can be created and deployed on the nodes of a K8s cluster (as Deployment or Daemonset) detecting network properties, such as MTU size and bandwidth, but also measuring performance statistics, such as packet loss, delay, and jitter. cURL and wget can be used to directly access the K8s REST API, monitor the availability and web server responsiveness of applications deployed in K8s as well as monitor the services' health. JMeter is a load testing tool designed for testing the performance and scalability of web applications (HTTP benchmarking), supporting features such as stress testing and distributed load testing.

90 <https://github.com/intrig-unicamp/mininet-wifi>

91 <https://github.com/containernet/containernet>

92 <https://github.com/openconfig/kne>

93 <https://github.com/IBM/k8s-netsim>

94 <https://github.com/coreemu/core>

95 <https://github.com/adjacentlink/emane>

96 <https://www.estinet.com/ns/>

97 <https://github.com/omnetpp/omnetpp>

98 <https://gitlab.com/nsnam/ns-3-dev/>

99 <https://github.com/kastenhq/kubestr>

100 <https://github.com/aquasecurity/kube-bench>

101 <https://github.com/vmware-tanzu/k-bench>

102 <https://github.com/cau-se/theodolite>

Referring to the multi-cluster experimentation approach, real-time monitoring/ observability operators and performance visualization tools are essential in multi-cluster K8s environments to provide insights into the health and performance of clusters, nodes, or individual pods. Such tools include Netdata¹⁰³, Prometheus¹⁰⁴, Grafana¹⁰⁵, Datadog¹⁰⁶, Pixie¹⁰⁷ while Thanos¹⁰⁸ and Mimir¹⁰⁹ can enhance/extend the monitoring and storage capabilities of multi-cluster environments.

Finally, chaos engineering tools can be utilized to systematically introduce controlled failures and disruptions into a system to assess its resilience and identify potential weaknesses. When applied to containerized applications - in the CODECO context - these tools enable the deliberate injection of failures, such as network disruptions, container termination, or resource constraints to check the fault tolerance of containers and workloads and enhance the containerized applications' resilience. Some popular tools include Chaos Mesh¹¹⁰, Chaos Toolkit¹¹¹, Litmus/LitmusChaos¹¹², gremlin¹¹³, Comcast¹¹⁴, Pumba¹¹⁵, kube-monkey¹¹⁶, Toxiproxy¹¹⁷.

Several open test-beds can facilitate the deployment and validation of the CODECO technologies and used for the experimentation of multi-cluster solutions such as Fed4FIRE [86]¹¹⁸, GENI [87]¹¹⁹, and EdgeNet [88]¹²⁰. The federated Fed4FIRE and GENI testbeds provide dynamic hardware resources reservation and allocation around the globe allowing for multi-cluster deployments and testing at large-scale. They also provide automations in the resource discovery and allocation with control tools (e.g., GUIs, CLI) such as jFed CLI¹²¹ and geni-lib¹²². In contrast, EdgeNet is a global K8s cluster, accessed through a Web-based interface and a user-specific config file which provides role-based access control. It provides custom EdgeNet objects and resources with a few basic features described in sub-section 4.3.

4.1.2 Guidelines

In this subsection, we lay out the initial guidelines regarding the experimentation methodology of the CODECO framework, but also on its constituting components.

To devise our initial system validation plan, we consider methodologies used in representative related works. According to the ACM SIGSOFT Empirical Standard for Benchmarking¹²³ a benchmark consists of four essential components, namely: the quality to be benchmarked, the metrics quantifying the quality, the measurements methods, and the system status during measurement time (e.g., workload, usage profile, tasks). We try to address these aspects in our methodology.

To this end, we firstly collect a set of potential measurements and the corresponding evaluation metrics. Some indicative metrics are the Pod readiness time [89], the Pod removal

103 <https://www.netdata.cloud/>

104 <https://github.com/prometheus/prometheus>

105 <https://grafana.com/>

106 <https://www.datadoghq.com/>

107 <https://github.com/pixie-io/pixie>

108 <https://github.com/thanos-io/thanos>

109 <https://github.com/grafana/mimir>

110 <https://github.com/chaos-mesh/chaos-mesh>

111 <https://github.com/chaostoolkit/chaostoolkit>, <https://github.com/chaostoolkit/chaostoolkit-kubernetes>

112 <https://github.com/litmuschaos/litmus>

113 <https://www.gremlin.com/>

114 <https://github.com/tylertreat/comcast>

115 <https://github.com/alexlei-led/pumba>

116 <https://github.com/asobti/kube-monkey>

117 <https://github.com/Shopify/toxiproxy>

118 <https://www.fed4fire.eu/>

119 <https://www.geni.net/>

120 <https://www.edge-net.org/>

121 <https://doc.ilabt.imec.be/jfed-documentation/>

122 <https://geni-lib.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

123 <https://acmsigsoft.github.io/EmpiricalStandards/docs/?standard=Benchmarking>

time, the number of failed requests, the load balancer's overhead, measures on the distribution of requests, as well as networking-related metrics such as throughput, RTT, packet loss. Aiming to track the performance metrics and evaluate the consistency of CODECO under different system conditions, we review methodological aspects considered in the state-of-the-art [89]. First, baseline experiments are usually performed, wherein nodes are in an "idle" state, i.e., running but not performing any cluster operations. This allows us to measure latencies associated with create and delete operations. To measure other latency types, more sophisticated experimental setups are required, involving operations, such as restart, update. For example, to evaluate failure detection, re-start and recovery time system crashes are simulated by terminating containers abruptly, while users keep sending requests to obtain metrics, such as failed requests (e.g., based on chaos engineering tools). Certain operations of secondary importance, like image pulls, may be omitted through warm-up runs which ensure that images are already present on nodes upon experiment initialisation. In any case, delays should intervene between operations (e.g., via hard-coded waiting times) to achieve realistic conditions and allow the resources to settle down. Moreover, for more complex aspects such as scalability, the resource demand and load capacity metrics have been proposed¹²⁴, and can be evaluated by varying load and resources combinations to assess the system's ability to scale and handle demands, while maintaining satisfactory QoS. Pertinent tools (e.g., Theodolite) are available for this purpose.

In the data plane, stress scenarios [29] in which multiple Pods/clusters are initiated in parallel to exhaust available resources are considered to assess the system's performance and resource utilization under heavy workloads. To evaluate networking aspects, both intra-node and inter-node communication are considered in related work [91] with respect to both Pod(s)-to-Pod(s) and Pod(s)-to-service(s) communication. Requests are exchanged among nodes (e.g., in an all-to-all or in a one-to-all request mode) to create multiple routes. Such setup is well-suited for testing the CODECO's NetMA performance, even assuming different networking topologies configurations, e.g., including links with same bandwidth vs heterogeneous scenarios [92]. The work in [91] focuses on the performance comparison of CNI plugins, and evaluates throughput and RTT, but also the communication overhead. Two scenarios are used: intra-node performance to better assess the communication overhead that stems from routing and the interaction with the host network stack, and inter-node communication.

Overall, orchestration frameworks are typically tested with different numbers of nodes and workloads. The most widely used tool to generate workload is K-Bench¹²⁵. During benchmarking, we also consider generating workload using EdgeNet-hosted clients based on defined selectors (e.g., geo-location).

Attack resilience is also an aspect of particular interest. Security will be ensured by the ACM component and built upon the OCM Submariner tool. Attack resilience will be evaluated against some widely known attack vectors (e.g., flooding, black-hole, or reverse attacks), by imitating sophisticated attacker behaviour and assessing their impact on CODECO performance. Advanced attack detection methods will be assessed, including novel supervised and unsupervised anomaly detection techniques [93], with the involvement of the PDLC component.

Finally, health-testing can be utilized to assess the stability of the system, for example measuring the execution time of the health check, since the latter tends to grow, when the system gradually becomes underperforming, e.g., due to a high resource utilization. An

124 <https://www.theodolite.rocks/concepts/metrics.html>

125 <https://github.com/vmware-tanzu/k-bench>

interesting approach is to combine health check tools (e.g., active monitor¹²⁶) with checks based on A workflows¹²⁷ and utilize anomaly detection methods to predict reliability issues¹²⁸. In CODECO, we also aim to contribute to the state-of-the-art, by devising a concrete methodology that fits the needs of multi-cluster solutions' benchmarking. To this end, we are currently considering potential extensions of existing tools so that they support multi-clusters. One promising direction is to extend the k8s-bench-suite¹²⁹, i.e., a scripts collection to benchmark K8s cluster performance (e.g., using knb, a lightweight script for network benchmarking on a target Kubernetes cluster), to enable the automated benchmarking in multi-clusters. These tests also include measurements (e.g., throughput and latency) between pods and services deployed in different clusters. For example, the OCM Hub cluster may also act as an experimentation controller for managed clusters. The former can be configured (via yaml manifest files) and then, automatically control the experiments over the managed clusters, appropriately.

The main purpose is to evaluate CODECO with respect to the CODECO KPIs, as defined in the GA. For instance, we plan to monitor the time taken to setup and configure multiple applications on a single cluster across Edge-Cloud, but the time taken to setup and configure federated clusters, as well. Such metrics will be monitored via well-established multi-cluster monitoring tools, such as Thanos. Similarly, the level of automation achieved during single clusters, but also multi-clusters deployment is crucial. The achieved level can be extracted via the built-in information of automation tools (e.g., ansible).

To evaluate CODECO components, we will rely on suitable metrics, having as starting point the KPIs provided in the GA Annex II (DoA); in deliverable D8 (Use-cases). For instance, ACM can be evaluated with respect to system metrics, such as CPU or memory utilization, the energy consumption per node, the number of failures, or volume of failures of a node. SWM can rely on metrics that have been used for the seamless computing work [30] evaluation, e.g., the migration time comprising the time the scheduler takes to detect the change and restart a new node. NetMA evaluation might rely on de-facto networking metrics or others like number of hops traversed, lifetime (i.e., counts with the node average consumed energy and link consumed energy).

4.2 CODECO Experimentation Environments

The CODECO experimentation environments belong into three categories: i) the use-case testbeds and lab experiments, referring to the provided experimentation facilities from partners, ii) the CODECO deployment and implementation environment, a multi-cluster environment based on public cloud resources and clusters provided from partners, and iii) The EdgeNet open test-bed facility (and its extensions), providing in a straightforward manner CODECO technologies to external users. A brief description of the three infrastructure types follows.

4.2.1 Use-case testbeds

This subsection primarily focuses on the deployment environments provided by CODECO partners, aiming to utilize CODECO in specific use-case applications and evaluate its performance in these experimental environments. Thus, six (6) use-cases shall be deployed as the basis for experimentation and demonstrations in operational environments across four (4) different European markets/domains: Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing and Smart Buildings. A short description of the different infrastructures follows:

126 <https://github.com/keikoproj/active-monitor>

127 <https://argoproj.github.io/argo-workflows/>

128 <https://medium.com/keikoproj/aiops-simple-anomaly-detection-in-kubernetes-with-active-monitor-and-tensorflow-24727c1606e5>

129 <https://github.com/InfraBuilder/k8s-bench-suite>

- **P1 - UGOE / City of Göttingen** will provide a Smart-city deployment based on IoT LoRa/LoRaWAN sensing infrastructure and shall integrate CODECO in different operational environments across the city such as mobile Edge nodes (i.e., CODECO toolkits in buses and smart Apps).
- **P2 - i2CAT premises** will provide a heterogeneous urban sensing infrastructure (next to university campus & highway) including traffic cameras and real-time data, On Board Units (OBUs), V2X Roadside Units (RSUs), cloud servers, edge devices, vehicles, smart 5G Customer Premise Equipments (CPEs) and 5G network infrastructure; and shall use the CODECO Edge-cloud continuum framework on the infrastructure side of the use-case.
- **P3 - TID's lab facilities and ICOM's fs|cdn - commercial future-proof CDN platform** (coordinated by TID, ICOM and UPM) will provide commercial networking equipment and state-of-the-art computer environments for media delivery (SDN/NFV testbed, metro-core network, and core control plane lab).
- **P4 - UPM premises/testbed** will provide the deployment of Edge-based Smart Energy Nodes to assist in the LECEMS (Local Energy Community Energy Management System) over buildings with different energy requirements (3 campuses and over 30 buildings equipped with PV Panels, Smart Meters, Shift Demand Managers, Electric Vehicles & Chargers, and real energy related data).
- **P5 - Fortiss IIoT Lab** will provide an experimental environment based on realistic Industrial IoT scenarios, including multiple devices, field-level, Edge (AGV mobile robots with sensors) and Cloud (AGVs controller node) nodes – with at least 10 Edge nodes, mobile and embedded – while the CODECO framework shall be installed across the fortiss IIoT Lab.
- **P6 - Crownstone Platform/Application Deployment** will provide its smart buildings use-case platform and application including Crownstone nodes, hubs, USB bridges and Smart building sensors & actuators.

4.2.2 CODECO Deployment and Implementation Environment

The CODECO framework is open-source and shall be made available to the community via **the Eclipse CODECO research GitLab**¹³⁰. This repository shall be fed via different repositories provided by different partners and worked directly.

In this context, **in terms of deployment and implementation, Partner ICOM provides a private GitLab repository** and supports the overall code integration and deployment over time.

Hence, for testing and validation, partners rely on local facilities. However, in CODECO, Partners shall also rely on a **common experimental infrastructure** which shall consider individual, local clusters provided by partners and a common Cloud space will be managed and maintained by Partner IBM. Partners will use the shared Cloud resources to develop and test the CODECO framework, in interconnection with local clusters provided by a few partners, such as the ICOM provided cluster. The design of this experimental framework shall be developed in WP5, which starts in M7. An overview on the current individual clusters and which are expected to be interconnected (via EdgeNet or the CODECO shared Cloud K8s environment) being planned is provided in Table 6.

130 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

Table 6: CODECO individual clusters and potential interconnections via a shared Cloud space.

Partner	Testbed Title	Purpose	Cluster(s)	EdgeNet or shared
FOR	IIoT Lab/Use-case P5	Deployment of realistic industrial IoT scenarios	10 edge nodes (mobile and embedded) – 1 to 5 clusters	Yes
ATOS	Internal testbed	Monitoring architecture	1 cluster for testing, currently K3s	No
ICOM	fs cdn™		1 cluster, 2 nodes	Yes (security restrictions)
ICOM ATH	K8S Cluster	For executing CI/CD pipelines	1 private cluster	No Yes
UGOE	Use-case P1	smart-city deployment, based on IoT LoRa/LoRaWAN infrastructure (stadtwerke-Goettingen)	1-2 clusters	No
SIE	Internal testbed	SWM development	1-2 clusters, internal testing	No
I2CAT	Use-case P2	Heterogeneous urban sensing infrastructure, including cloud servers, edge devices, vehicles, 5G network capabilities	1-2 clusters	To be defined
TID	TID's lab facilities	TID: Commercial networking equipment and state-of-the-art computer environments for media delivery UC3M: UC3M: three K8 clusters, including one of high availability.	1-5 clusters	No
UPM	UPM premises	energy mangement over buildings with different requirements (3 campuses, over 30 buildings)	1-3 clusters	To be defined
ALM	Crownstone smart buildings solution	smart building solutions, e.g., energy demand and indoor tracking	Crownstone Nodes; Crownstone Bridges; Crownstone Hubs	
IBM	Public Cloud Resources	Plans to have internal testing; closed.	Share Cloud, min 3 clusters, expected 10	No

Via the common Cloud space, CODECO Partners will be able to install and run the latest or mock versions of individual components to be tested along with other components. This methodology is expected to allow for the seamless development and integration of CODECO components, but also ensure the smooth end-to-end communication between the components' APIs.

The shared resources will be allocated among the CODECO partners, to avoid relying on the private resources of each organization due to the associated security threats. For instance, K8s cluster(s) with sufficient and adjustable resources can be allocated, with each partner using the shared resources and reporting on their test activities to ensure the efficient resource usage/allocation.

We are currently in the process of deciding the configuration of resources that we plan to allocate from public cloud offerings. Our starting point is an initial assessment of the minimum demands of main technologies utilized by CODECO, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Minimum system requirements of technologies utilized by CODECO.

Technology	Minimum System Requirements					Node type
	Node type	OSS	CPU/vCPU	RAM (GB)	Disk (GB)	
OpenShift/OCM/ACM ¹³¹	Master	Red Hat Enterprise Linux (RHEL) 7.5, or RHEL Atomic Host 7.4.5 or later.	4 CPU; 4 vCPU	16	42	Medium
	Worker		1 vCPU	8	32	Medium
	External etcd				20	Medium
	Ansible controller			0.075 GB (75 MB)		small
Microshift		Red Hat Enterprise Linux (RHEL) Extended Update Support (EUS) (9.2 or later)	- x86_64 or aarch64 CPU architecture - 2 CPU cores	2	2	Small
K3s		- RHEL9, Ubuntu, openSUSE Leap, Oracle Linux, Rocky Linux and SLES - Red Hat/CentOS Enterprise Linux and Raspberry Pi OS with additional setup	- x86_64 or armhf or arm64/aarch64 or s390x CPU architecture - 1 CPU core	0.512 GB (512MB)		Small

Finally, the CODECO shared Cloud infrastructure will also be used for the integration of the complete CODECO framework in the context of the use cases to allow for the development, testing, and public demonstrations. These resources will be supplementary to other resources that we are going to exploit; most notably, the EdgeNet-based CODECO framework that is the primary testbed. EdgeNet has been chosen as widely-known experimental platform suitable for large-scale experiments, where nodes from around the globe can be interconnected, that has been used in several use-cases, e.g. for internet-scale tests [86][94]; for workload generation[95]. Our plan to exploit its capabilities is thoroughly explained in the following subsection.

4.3 EdgeNet Experimentation Guidelines

Regarding EdgeNet, the focus is the experimentation with CODECO technologies by “external” users and the research community in an open testbed with single or multi-cluster domains.

EdgeNet is a distributed edge cloud implemented as a set of K8s extensions based on CRs. Some basic features can be found in Figure 23 including¹³²: (i) Selective Deployment & Node selection: assign labels through scheduler, allow geolocation- based deployments and pick up nodes through a selector; (ii) Authority (Permission management): through a user-specific kubeconfig file provided by EdgeNet after the registration and a role-based access control (RoleBinding K8s object); (iii) Teams: create a namespace for the participants to create slices independently; (iv) Slicing: among nodes to form isolated subclusters (SliceClaim) by defining a selector - creates a namespace with a resource quota in which defined users participate; (v) Isolation: experimenters are assigned their own namespace to interact with EdgeNet.

131 <https://docs.openshift.com/container-platform/3.11/install/prerequisites.html>

132 <https://github.com/EdgeNet-project/edgenet/tree/main/docs>

Figure 23: EdgeNet CRDs and features.

CODECO shall be integrated into the large-scale, worldwide EdgeNet experimental infrastructure, designing an experimentation framework to assist in the building of experimentation and novel concepts by the research community, while partners shall deploy large-scale experiments based on the CODECO EdgeNet framework, across multiple domains. CODECO aspires to deploy the Open Edge-Cloud Toolkit on EdgeNet to perform integration, testing and validation of the different components (concerning performance aspects such as latency, energy consumption and scalability), based on pre-selected CODECO use-cases.

Regarding the experimentation in EdgeNet, additional actions shall be taken such as contributing new nodes to increase the presence of nodes in the system, considering the implemented scenarios/use-cases, clarifying the provided tools/limitations, and resolving issues. At the time of this document ATH and FOR have contributed nodes to the EdgeNet project while certain partners (ICOM, I2CAT) have plans to integrate EdgeNet nodes and additional partners are also anticipated to do so. An interactive map of the worldwide geographically distributed EdgeNet nodes can be found in¹³³. Furthermore, the federated deployment of CODECO in EdgeNet is currently under discussion since the relevant capabilities are under development from the EdgeNet team.

5 Open-source CODECO Ecosystem Guidelines

The section describes the guidelines and infrastructure that the CODECO project has put in place to host its open-source code and to manage its interactions with early adopters, along with supporting open-source best practices such as transparency, openness, meritocracy, and vendor neutrality.

133 <https://www.edge-net.org/>

5.1 Open-Source Governance and the Eclipse Development Process

Professional open-source projects are governed according to certain rules, processes, and best practices to manage contributions and development by diverse communities. This is especially important for vendor-neutral open-source projects which are not managed by a single entity. The aim for CODECO open-source assets is to become community-driven, vendor-neutral open-source projects.

The Eclipse Development Process defines the processes and rules, governance structures and definitions, project roles, releases and reviews, and interaction between projects and the community¹³⁴.

The very basis for setting up a successful open-source project with proper governance is the project creation. Figure 24 shows the process of project creation at the Eclipse Foundation.

Figure 24: The Eclipse project creation process.

It starts with a proposal describing the project, the content of the code, the license used, the project leader and the first committers. The proposal is made available to the community for review for two weeks. At the end of the community review period, the creation review begins with a trademark review. After the creation review, the project is created and provisioning can begin, i.e., moving the code to the Eclipse Foundation infrastructure and ensuring that the committers paperwork is in place (contributor/committer agreements). After the project is provisioned, an Intellectual Property (IP) review is performed to identify potential issues such as missing copyrights, copying code, or incompatible licenses between dependencies or with the license selected by the project. Finally, once the IP review is complete, the initial contribution is released. It can be safely shared with the rest of the world.

The initial contribution when creating a new project consists of a piece of code of various sizes and may belong to a single organization or different organizations. Contributing a single piece of code, for a single organization, is straightforward and takes between 2 weeks and 2 months for the creation and the IP review. Conversely, in case of a large piece of code and/or many contributors from different organizations, which is the case for a research project, this exercise can take a lot of time and effort. In such a context, the Eclipse Foundation has found that this can slow down the project, which is not desirable as the task usually occurs in the last few months of the research project.

¹³⁴ <https://www.eclipse.org/projects/handbook/>

Therefore, we have adapted the project creation process to research projects, allowing project partners to get used to open-source best practices and account for the research and development tasks performed during a research project. **Eclipse Research Labs** aims at gradually and continuously preparing research results to becoming proper open-source projects during the research project lifetime.

5.2 Implementing Open-Source Best Practices: the Eclipse CODECO Research Lab

Eclipse Research Labs is a combination of infrastructure (GitLab) and trainings to implement open-source best practices right from the start and increase the chances of delivering high-quality, professional open-source results. In concrete terms, this means enabling:

- **Open Collaboration:** An open infrastructure (GitLab) has been provided for CODECO consortium collaborate in the open early, which is one of the main guidelines for doing open-source successfully in research projects. It also enables good practices of (open-source) software development such as integrating often and soon, automating the process with continuous testing and integration scripts to identify bugs or broken APIs (Application Programming Interface) as early as possible.
- **Transparency:** It encourages the consortium to work openly: realizing that the code is in the middle of hundreds of millions of public repositories and may go unnoticed, expressing the development plan clearly and openly throughout the process and expressing your decisions clearly and transparently, avoiding drowning them in internal emails. It also eases the communication of early project results to external stakeholders.
- **Community Governance:** Contributor Agreements allow to identify and list the contributors to the open-source project(s) from beginning. Signing the Eclipse Contributor Agreement (ECA)¹³⁵ is a prerequisite for pushing code in one of the CODECO Research Labs repositories. Further information on why an ECA is required and what it is for can be found in the ECA FAQ¹³⁶.
- **Open-Source Licenses:** It is important to select appropriate licenses for the CODECO outputs, depending on the intended means of exploitation. In the “default cases” this will be EPL-2.0, Apache-2.0 or MIT. As all CODECO results should be commercially exploitable, GPL and similar strong copyleft licenses will be avoided.
- **IP Review:** IP reviews help to analyse shared code as early and often as possible to identify potential intellectual property issues, such as missing copyright headers in source files, metadata files in repositories or third-party dependencies with incompatible licenses (alternative compatible libraries can be used).

The Eclipse Research Labs GitLab is hosted by OVH and is in France; it is important for the Eclipse Foundation, located in Europe, and for a European research project to be hosted and managed in Europe, following the European laws on privacy and data protection.

Implementing these best practices will allow the project partners to work in a professional open-source environment - based on proven Eclipse Foundation practices – and ease the transition from research results into proper Eclipse Foundation open-source projects. Furthermore, this approach gives the consortium the room to experiment and define the scope of the resulting open-source projects. This approach is depicted in Figure 25 and is usually realized in three phases:

135 <https://www.eclipse.org/legal/ECA.php>

136 <https://www.eclipse.org/legal/ecafaq.php>

- **Phase 1: Identification of code to open-source (M1 – M12).** The CODECO consortium selects the parts of the CODECO architecture that are going to be open-source. These parts are immediately moved to the Eclipse Research Labs. Additional open-source components can be moved to Research Labs, while any CODECO component may be created directly in the Eclipse Research Labs if it is intended to be open-source.
- **Phase 2: Open collaboration development (M7 – M36).** During this phase research and development takes place and we ensure the implementation of the open-source best practices and governance principles (transparency, openness, IP-analyses, contributor agreements).
- **Phase 3: Eclipse project creation (M24 – beyond project).** When the consortium decides to release a component (or a set thereof) as vendor-neutral open-source project, the process of moving the project to become a “real” Eclipse Foundation project can be kicked off (as described in section 5.1). Thanks to the Research Labs approach, the necessary open-source good practices are already in place, so this step will in most cases be very smooth.

Figure 25: Eclipse Research Labs Phases.

The indicated timings of the phases are a rough timeframe. Usually, the phases are overlapping, due to the quite agile nature of research projects and the diversity of parties involved.

Figure 26 shows an indicative timeline, based on the main CODECO outputs related to open-source.

Figure 26: CODECO open-source timeline.

In M2, the Eclipse CODECO Research Labs¹³⁷ has been provisioned and by the date of writing 27 developers signed the Contributor Agreement and joined the CODECO GitLab. Initial repositories have been created according to the CODECO main components, see Figure 27. The next step is moving initial code to the Research Labs GitLab, integrating with potential partner’s repositories and setup the CI/CD process, coordinated by WP3. Following a code-first approach, once code is pushed, license compliance and third-party IP checks will be started. Thus, collaborative development in the open is starting M6, aiming at having an initial snapshot of the CODECO open-source toolkit in M9 and the first intermediate release at M18. It is expected to start the creation of Eclipse Projects from Research Labs components around M24.

Figure 27: The CODECO Eclipse GitLab repositories.

137 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

To facilitate the open-source work to the partners and to help understand the open-source best practices, two training sessions were provided to the consortium by the time of writing:

- Open-Source Ecosystem, in February 2023, two-hours online workshop.
- Open-Source Licensing and Compliance, June 2023, two-hours online workshop.

It should be noted that besides creating new CODECO open-source assets, partners will also contribute upstream to existing open-source projects and communities. These efforts and the related community building activities are addressed in *Task 7.1: Toolkits Exploitation and Open-source Community Building* and the related deliverables *D7.1-3 CODECO ecosystem community building report*.

6 Summary and Next Steps

The CODECO Deliverable D9 covers the work that has been developed in the first six months of the CODECO *Work Package 2 (WP2)*, tasks 2.2 (*Technological Boundaries and Global Validation Design Aspects*), tasks 2.3 (*Open-source CODECO Ecosystem Design*), and task 2.4 (*CODECO architectural design*).

The deliverable covers the high-level CODECO architectural design, providing input to the overall high-level specification, key technologies, interfaces, and expected operation within a single cluster. Considerations for the federated clusters' operation are also made.

In addition to the architectural design, D9 provides guidelines to be adopted in the project concerning the CODECO key innovation contributions and CODECO experimentation and validation.

The work presented in Deliverable D9 shall be continued in WP3, WP5, and WP7. WP3 shall further continue with the development of the CODECO framework and its operation for a single cluster. WP5 shall address experimentation and validation aspects, taking into consideration the guidelines described in sections 4 and 5. WP7 shall further develop the CODECO ecosystem, by considering the proposed methodology and timeline detailed in section 5.

Finally, the current architectural design shall be developed in WP3, and resumed from M14 to M18 of the project, when the final architectural design of CODECO is expected to be provided.

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Annex I – Example of CODECO Metrics: Data, Compute, User, Network

In this annex we provide examples of metrics that are being integrated in CODECO, to increase the orchestration adaptability capability. The table provides the following fields:

- **Comp** – CODECO component.
- **Cat** – refer to section 2.4.4, categories of metrics initially considered in CODECO.
- **Type** – metric type, e.g., vector, scalar, string.
- **Def** – brief explanation and units, if available.
- **Source** – how the metric is requested to be considered, e.g., CODECO Application Model (CAM) or via a CRD/CR from a component.
- **Mon** – how is the metric monitored.
- **Upd** – which component oversees updating the metric.
- **Avail** – Availability of the metric in K8s currently, i.e., whether the parameter can be currently obtained from K8s APIs or plugins. New means it is a new metric; yes, means it is readily available; partially means that there are some modifications required.
- **Relevancy** – Brief justification for the proposed use of the metric.

Metric Definition					Metric Realization				Relevancy
Comp	Cat	Id	Type	Def	Source	Mon	Upd	Avail	
ACM	User	Geo-location of user	Vector	Geo-location is defined longitude and latitude of the user location	CAM	kubelet	K8s	NEW	User preferences may assist in improving QoE, by providing the user with additional control level
ACM	User	userid	Scalar.Integer	UID	CAM	kubelet	K8s	yes	
ACM	User	usergroup	Scalar.Integer	GID	CAM	kubelet	K8s	yes	
ACM	Compute	QoS class	Scalar.Integer	Currently 3 levels of QoS are provided by K8s; here the aim would be for the user to provide a specific QoS class. We could align with DiffServ (DSCP) as it is the basis for QoS in IP (Guaranteed, Burstable, BE); OpenShift mentions QoS DSCP.	CAM; CRD spec resource (request, limit)	kubelet	K8s	partially	Extend the existing K8s behaviour, to improve aspects such as load balancing and realizing a fine-grained node scoring
ACM	Compute	cpu	Scalar.Integer	CPU represents compute processing available on nodes and is specified in units of Kubernetes CPUs. Limits and requests for CPU resources are measured in cpu units. In Kubernetes, 1	CAM; CRD spec resource (request, limit)	kubelet	K8s	NEW	

Metric Definition					Metric Realization				Relevancy
Comp	Cat	Id	Type	Def	Source	Mon	Upd	Avail	
				CPU unit is equivalent to 1 physical CPU core, or 1 virtual core, depending on whether the node is a physical host or a virtual machine running inside a physical machine. The Linux Kernel provides the CPU status					
ACM	Compute	memory	Scalar.Integer	MEM represents compute memory available on nodes. Limits and requests for memory are measured in bytes. You can express memory as a plain integer or as a fixed-point number using one of these quantity suffixes: E, P, T, G, M, k. Note: Mebibyte (Mi): 1 MiB = 1.048 MB	CAM; CRD spec resource (request, limit)	kubelet	K8s	NEW	
ACM	Compute	Energy consumption, node	Scalar.Float	Requested energy consumption - to be better defined	CRD spec codeco-compute: (new) , energy (request, limit)	Kepler/Prometheus	k8s ¹³⁸	Yes	
ACM	Compute	resilience	Scalar.Integer	Number of failures, or volume of failures of a node	CRD spec codeco-compute: (new) , resilience (request, limit)	Prometheus (node failures); MDM;	MDM	partially ¹³⁹	
ACM	Compute	security	String	Security defines set of communication encryption information related to the level and type of security the	CRD spec codeco-compute: (new) (request, limit). - Node	kubelet	k8s ¹⁴⁰	NEW	

138 Kubelet can track it. If it can only be defined as an integer than it is rounded up to nearest whole number.

139 Partial support, as K8s lacks logs aggregation to get this specific inferred metric. The metric would require an audit support, which may be provided by MDM (log collection and aggregation).

140 Definition of

Metric Definition					Metric Realization				Relevancy
Comp	Cat	Id	Type	Def	Source	Mon	Upd	Avail	
				node features to prevent security breaches.	attributes defintion.				
ACM	Compute	compute specs	String	Defines the node type of processing and memory disk units. (e.g SSD, HDD, GPU, #CPUs (parallisim), accelerator processing units)	CAM	kubelet	K8s ¹⁴¹	yes	
NetMA	NetNode	ebw	Scalar. Float	node egress bandwidth, bytes	NetMA CRD; request: minbandwidth ; limit: maxbandwidth	New component extension, ALTO, Prometheus - see netperf	NetMA	partial ¹⁴²	Integrate network awareness at a node level. A cloud or edge "node" needs to address node usage, but also network usage
NetMA	NetNode	ibw	Scalar. Float	node ingress bandwidth, bytes	NetMA CRD; request: latency (minimum bounded latency expected); limit: maximum bounded latency tolerated	New component extension, ALTO, Prometheus - see netperf	NetMA	partial	
NetMA	NetNode	congestion	Scalar. Integer	itrafic vs etrafic	NetMA CRD; request: expected congestion level (0-100, %)	NetMA via prometheus	NetMA	NEW	
NetMA	NetNode	packetloss	Scalar. Integer	based on the node monitoring	NetMA CRD; request: expected packet loss level (0-100, %)	NetMA via prometheus	NetMA	NEW	
NetMA	NetNode	UID visits	Matrix	May be relevant in case of mobile environments, UID visits to a node, for instance. Can be based on nr of visits x duration of visit.	NetMA CRD; request/limit - tbd	New component extension, NetMA	NetMA	NEW	

141 Each worker node has compute specs attributes, which is compared to compute specs in a % of matching score.

142 see the plugin network-aware scheduling, <https://github.com/kubernetes-sigs/scheduler-plugins/blob/master/pkg/networkaware/>

Metric Definition					Metric Realization				Relevancy
Comp	Cat	Id	Type	Def	Source	Mon	Upd	Avail	
NetMA	NetNode	Zone	String	Associated to an inter or intra-routing approach; inter, AS	NetMA CRD; request, AS or geographical zone, e.g. , DE	New component extension, NetMA	NetMA	partial, see network-aware scheduler	
NetMA	NetNode	nodedegree	Scalar.Integer	In a network, the degree of a node is defined as the sum of all edges connected to it (later, ingress and egress links)	NetMA CRD; request, AS or geographical zone, e.g. , DE	New component extension, NetMA	NetMA	NEW	
NetMA	NetNode	betweenness		Betweenness centrality. The nr of avg shortest paths passing by a node in a network. The simplest form of BC is the ratio of all the shortest paths between the other nodes to the total number of these shortest paths that pass through the node,	NetMA CRD; request/limit - tbd	New component extension, NetMA	NetMA	NEW	
NetMA	NetLink	reliability	Scalar.Float	Link should be available 95% of the time	NetMA CRD; request/limit - tbd	New component extension, NetMA	NetMA	NEW	The network awareness needs to consider also link metrics, to allow for an adequate deployment and network adaptation
NetMA	NetLink	throughput	Scalar.Float	expected link throughput	NetMA CRD; request/limit - tbd	New component extension, NetMA	NetMA	NEW	
NetMA	NetLink	latency		Based on RTT	NetMA CRD; request/limit - tbd	New component extension, NetMA	NetMA	NEW	
NetMA	NetLink								
NetMA	NetworkTopology	pathlength	Scalar.Integer	Number of hops traversed; Average Shortest Path Length	NetMA CRD, request (expected average nr of hops); limit (maximum allowed number of hops)	New component extension, NetMA	NetMA	NEW	Important assuming the need to reduce latency across components of an app, etc.
NetMA	NetworkTopology	energyefficiency	Scalar.Float				PDLC	NEW	
NetMA	NetworkTopology	Lifetime		Counts with the node consumed energy (avg)	NetMA CRD, levels, e.g., 0-5 (5 highly inefficient)	New component extension	PDLC	NEW	

Metric Definition					Metric Realization				Relevancy
Comp	Cat	Id	Type	Def	Source	Mon	Upd	Avail	
				and link consumed energy.		on, NetMA			
MDM	NodeData	freshness	String	Measuring the healthiness of a node, to whether it can ensure that new or updated data of its existing workload is processed in a timely fashion and that the dataset grows in stable specified size.	MDM CRD, request, and limit	New component extension, MDM	MDM	NEW	Brings an additional level of observability to K8s.
MDM	NodeData	compliance	String	Data Compliance refers to the desired adherence to regulations and policies derived from geographical zones regulation, etc	MDM CRD spec, data compliance (annotations?)	New component extension, MDM	MDM	NEW	
MDM	NodeData	portability		How effective the application workload performs in the current node in comparison to a former node	MDM CRD spec, data compliance (annotations?)	New component extension, MDM	MDM	NEW	

Annex II – CODECO High-Level Architecture Interfaces

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-ACM-PROM	Integration of the CODECO metrics into Prometheus	CRD	Bi-directional
I-ACM-MDM-1	Data collection from CRDs of other components, to be used in the MDM integration of the CODECO MDM operator.	CRD	Bi-directional
I-ACM-MDM-2	Integration of additional data types	To be defined	Input
I-ACM-PDLC-1	Integration of CA derived metrics into Prometheus	CRD	Input
I-ACM-PDLC-2	Use of CRDs from other components by PDLC	CRD	Output
I-ACM-NET-1	Integration of the NetMA CRD/CR(s) and respective operator(s)	CRD	Input
I-ACM-SWM-1	Integration of the SWM controller-manager (CRD/CR(s) via K8s API)	CR via K8s API (REST)	Bi-directional
I-ACM-MDM-1	Metadata derived from the CODECO CRDs (other components)	OAS REST	Input
I-ACM-MDM-2	Integration of additional data types into CRDs/CRs	To be defined	Output
I-ACM-PDLC-1	Knowledge graph shared to PDLC	OAS REST	Bi-directional
I-SWM-ACM-1	Access/integration with CRs/operators handled by SWM and other CODECO components, e.g., NetMA	CR	Bi-directional
I-SWM-ACM-2	Registration, configuration, and operation of QoS Scheduler	K8s scheduling framework	Bi-directional
I-PDLC-SWM-1,2	PDLC will set attributes of custom resources of the infrastructure model, which are used by SWM to influence the placement decision for workloads. This can relate to combined costs (I-PDLC-SWM-1) or to behaviour estimation (I-PDLC-SWM-2). Currently, the relevant custom resources are <i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i> . PDLC can also make use of the QoS Scheduler extensions.	CR	Input
I-SWM-PDLC-1	PDLC will be able to know about scheduling/placement decisions of SWM by accessing the <i>AssignmentPlan</i> CR	CR	Output
I-SWM-NET-1	Used to request NetMA to perform QoS reservations. SWM may perform requests for reservations to NetMA, based on the scheduling/placement decisions. Furthermore, NetMA may also handle network-related CRs (<i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i>) to reflect network conditions.	CR	Bi-directional
I-PDLC-ACM-1	Obtaining data collected by other CODECO components and made available via CRs of	CRs	Input

ID	Description	Type	Direction
	those components.		
I-PDLC-ACM-2	Output of the combined infrastructure view, via a PDLC CR	CR	Output
I-MDM-PDLC-1	Data collected by CODECO MDM	Knowledge graph, e.g., graphDB	Input
I-PDLC-SWM-1,2	PDLC will set attributes of custom resources of the infrastructure model, which are used by SWM to influence the placement decision for workloads. This can relate to combined costs (I-PDLC-SWM-1) or to behaviour estimation (I-PDLC-SWM-2). Currently, the relevant custom resources are <i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i> . PDLC can also make use of the QoS Scheduler extensions.	CR	Output
I-SWM-PDLC-1	PDLC will be able to know about scheduling/placement decisions of SWM by accessing the <i>AssignmentPlan</i> CR	CR	Input
I-NET-PDLC-1	NetMA asks infrastructure element estimation from PDLC-DL	CR	Output
I-ACM-NET-1	Integration of the NetMA CRD/CR(s) and respective operator(s)	CRD	Input
I-SWM-NET-1	Used to request NetMA to perform QoS reservations. SWM may perform requests for reservations to NetMA, based on the scheduling/placement decisions. Furthermore, NetMA may also handle network-related CRs (<i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i>) to reflect network conditions.	CR	Bi-directional
I-NET-PDLC-1	Request infrastructure estimation	CR	Input

